

- LEED W_2O ($x=0$ $y=-5$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$)
 2.4A , 3 mV screen, 0.7 μMCP
- 100 eV 0.4 V wehmet 120V focus, 70V grid, (19 μA , 0.94 μA)
- Lender
- $y-3$
- $y+3$
- $z+2$
- $z-2$
- ~~100~~ 70 eV 2.0 V wehmet (18 μA , 0.71 μA)
- 28 eV 0.0 V wehmet (13 μA , 0.26 μA)
- 47 eV 0.0 V wehmet (24 μA , 0.60 μA)

Outgassing oven after vent:
 $\hookrightarrow 31\text{V}$, 1.189 A (limit of supply) $\Rightarrow 550^\circ\text{C}$ (still rising slowly)
 pressure always $\sim 2 \times 10^{-7}$

Ar-mica sample heated to 500°C , no pressure spike ($p < 3 \times 10^{-7}$)
 $\hookrightarrow [24.76\text{V}, 1\text{A}]$

Friday, June 5th 2020

$f_{\text{AC,GAS}} = 2.7 \times 10^{-2}$ mbars, $f_{\text{AC,I}} = 3.5 \times 10^{-8}$ mbars, $f_{\text{AC,PRE}} = 6.9 \times 10^{-2}$ mbars, $f_{\text{LLS}} = 2.8 \times 10^{-3}$ mbars, $f_{\text{PC}} = 7.5 \times 10^{-10}$ mbars, $f_{\text{PC,PRE}} = 2.3 \times 10^{-2}$ mbars
 Hi-Z: all under range

Beam: @1000eV, 1.0 dets: $I_0 = 18.53\text{A}$ with $R_x = +0.521$, $R_y = -0.127$

Outgassing MCP to 1630V, Screen to 3600V

Beam roughly in place: tested with XAG, mag $x=12$, $y=-12.6$, $z=16$, $R=30^\circ$

Position optimized with Am-mica #2; @1000eV, 0.5 dets: $E_k = 911\text{eV}$, $E_p = 1002\text{eV}$: 3808 cps!

Frame: $z_1 = 18.92$, $z_2 = 13.39$, $z_3 = 14.42$, $x = 9.10$, $y = 50.3$, $WXY = 84.06$

$W = 84.06\text{um}$, $WXV = 27.13$, $WZV = -3.12$, $WZX = -1.35$, Beam level = 1396.6

SiN: $T_{rx} = 0.35$, $T_{ry} = 0.6$

XPS Am-mica #2

001 Survey, 1000eV, $E_p = 20\text{eV}$, 0.5 dets, 4.1h, Picture saved from camera
 $x=12$, $y=-11.25$, $z=26$, $R=30^\circ$

002 Am 4k, 100 meV step, same as 001

003 ~~Am 4k~~ lower part of angle ($x=12$, $y=-11.2$, $z=36$, $R=30^\circ$), 10.1h } Picture taken

004 Survey, lower part of angle, same as 003

005 Survey, $x=12$, $y=-11.15$, $z=46$, $R=30^\circ$, 4.1h } Picture taken

006 Am 4k, same position as 005

007 Am 4k, same as 005

008 Survey, $x=12$, $y=-11.15$, $z=56$, $R=30^\circ$, 4.1h } Picture taken

009 Am 4k, same position as 008

LEED @ 100eV: no spots observed

*LEED $W(111) + Cu_2O$ (After sputter/Anneal + 1 day of sitting in vacuum)
 2.4A 3W screen 0.7W MCP ($x=0, y=-5, z=267, \theta=60$)
 • 100eV, 3.4V wehnelt, 120V focus, 40V grid
 - center Cu_2O (16uA, 0.87uA)
 - center $W(111)$ (18uA, 0.92uA)
 - 70eV $W(111)$ center (18uA, 0.7uA)

$P_{vac} = 3.0 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar
 $Cu_2O(111)$ MHS

Energy ranges 1100eV $W 2p$ (125-170eV) $O 1s$ (548-570eV) $W 3p$ (995-1037)

010 XPS Survey 1100eV, slits 0.5, $R=800$ $x=12, y=-13, z=17.5, R=30^\circ, E_p=20eV$

011 XPS $Cu 2p$ 1100eV ($E_{kin}=125-170eV$), 100meV slits, $x=12, y=-13, z=17.5, R=30^\circ, E_p=20eV$

012 XPS $Cu 3p, O 1s$, 1100eV, same position as 011

~~013 Survey 1100eV, slits 0.5, $R=800$, $x=12, y=-13, z=17.5, R=30^\circ, E_p=20eV$~~

015 Survey 700eV, slits 1.0 x 1.0 10 iterations

Energy ranges 700eV $O 1s$ (151-173eV) $C 1s$ (400-417eV) $W 3p$ (595-631) VB (690-702)

017 $O 1s, Cu 3p, C 1s, VB$ @ 700eV, 1.0 slits, $E_p=20eV$. $x=12, y=-13, z=17.3, R=30^\circ$

RBN - $Cu(111)$

018 Survey 700eV slits 1.0 x 1.0 10 iterations $x=12, y=-11.4, z=17.3, R=30^\circ, E_p=20eV$

Additional energy ranges $B 1s$ (496-510eV) $N 1s$ (290-304eV) for 700eV

019 XPS $O 1s, W 3p, C 1s, VB, B 1s, N 1s$ @ 700eV, 1.0 slits $E_p=20eV$ $x=12, y=-11.4, z=17.4, R=30^\circ$

020 XPS " " @ 700eV, 1.0 slits $E_p=20eV$ $x=13, y=-11.3, z=17.4, R=30^\circ$

024 survey 1100 slits 1.0 x 1.0 10 iterations $x=13, y=-11.3, z=17.5, R=30, E_p=20eV$

025 XPS $Cu 2p, Cu 3p$, same position and settings as 024

min Can O_2 2019: 4.7 bar before dosing (purged); attach new "2020" can

026 XPS $Cu 3p, O 1s, C 1s, VB, B 1s, N 1s$ @ 700eV, 1.0 slits $E_p=20eV$ $x=13, y=-11.3, z=17.3$

start UHV => 19:57 MS started at 17:01 sequence "3"

Sequence 15: close Turbi gate valve, start looking O_2 from min Can 2019

=> 1×10^{-3} mbar reached at iteration 16 (Close GV at 19:00, Iteration 15)

5×10^{-2} mbar 17

8×10^{-1} mbar 18

1 mbar 19

24:00 in mass spec (19:28)

drill 1 mbar ~ 30m 20 -> 70

71 close beamline: Pt 100 seems defective, test beam effect stop seq at 01:50:00 20:53

029 XPS " same as 026" @ 700eV, 1.0 slits $E_p=20eV$ same pos as 026

start 29:20 (02:17:00 on MS)

Anneal => T (K) Iteration

	T (K)	Iteration	P (mbar)	Time MMS	V, I
	109.6 RT	1	9.6×10^{-1}	02:20:00	
ramp ↓	118.6	21	8.8×10^{-1}	02:47:00	3.2V, 0.29A
	120.8 (50°C)	71	1.1×10^0 mbar	04:10:00	3.2V, 0.28A
ramp ↓	137.6 (100°C)	88	1.1 mbar	04:39:00	5V, 0.52A
	138.9	137	1 mbar	06:06:00	4.9V, 0.5A
ramp ↓	157.4 (150°C)	151	1 mbar	06:29:30	6.2V / 0.73A
	157.6	200	1 mbar	08:02:00	6.2V / 0.72A
ramp ↓	174.6 (200°C)	221	1 mbar	08:41:30	7.55V / 0.98A
	176.5	270	9.8×10^{-1} mbar	10:30:00	7.4V / 0.977A

! after approx 15 minutes, spectra change $\rightarrow$ C removed, VB shape differed
 no B, N visible and Cu brighter
 $\Rightarrow$ removed ~~HBN~~ hBN from top?
 From C1s seems fairly sudden

$\rightarrow$ When cooled, Test if beam-induced by moving spot?
 or only thermal

VB resembles CuO2 (110), 0.1s appear feature of higher KE and gas phase shifts (charging?)

Cooldown	T (Ω)	Iteration	P	Time
$\downarrow$	$\sim$	271	1 mbar	10:32:00
	1105 (40°C)	2890	0.8 mbar	11:02:00
	111.6	305	1.1 mbar	11:44:00

Crystals changed color! Picture taken: surface rough!

110.7	315	0.9 mbar
-------	-----	----------

$z = 17.3 \xrightarrow{\text{max } P_0} 17.2$

~~XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX~~

$\lambda = 1 \text{ mbar} \rightarrow \text{HV } (> 5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mbar}), x=13, y=-11.3, z=17.2, R=30^\circ$

030 XPS "Same as 26/29" @ 700 eV 2.1×10^{-6} mbar "UHV"

031 Survey "Same as 30" @ 700 eV 9.1×10^{-8} mbar

032 XPS B 1s @ 700 eV "Same as 030"

033 Survey 1100 eV slits 0.5x0.5 12 iterations Same position 31 5.0×10^{-8} mbar

034 XPS O 1s, B 1s, W 2P, W 3P @ 1100 eV 0.5x0.5 slits, Same position

035 XPS O 1s, B 1s, W 2P, W 3P @ 1100 eV 0.5x0.5 slits, $x=12.5, y=-11.45, z=17.2, R=30$

036 XPS O 1s, C 1s, N 1s, B 1s, W 3P, VB, @ 700 eV 1x1 slits Same position as 035

hBN w foil

037 Survey 700 eV slits 1x1 12 iterations $x=13, y=-13.4, z=17.3, R=30$

Sputter W(11) $x=5, y=-2, z=3.8, \theta=315$ 140 min
 2.6×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

2.6 μ A sample

Anneal W(11) w/ e-Beam (1 keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$	P	0.07 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
16:10	$P = 2.7 \times 10^{-9}$	
16:11	$P = 1 \times 10^{-7}$	38 mA, 2.95 A, 14.92 V
16:13	$P = 3.6 \times 10^{-8}$	37.16 mA, 2.93 A, 14.92 V
16:16	$P = 1.9 \times 10^{-8}$	37.6 mA, 2.93 A, 15.00 V

038 XPS O 1s, C 1s, B 1s, N 1s, W 3P, VB 1x1 @ 700 eV Same spot as 037

039 Survey 1100 eV slits 0.5x0.5 10 iterations same spot as 038

Sputter W(11) $x=5, y=-2, z=3.8, \theta=315$ 140 min
 2.8×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

2.5 μ A sample

040 XPS O 1s B 1s W 2P W 3P 0.5x0.5 @ 1100 eV Same spot as 039

Anneal W(11) w/ eBeam 1 keV

Start $\Rightarrow$	P	0.1 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
17:32	$P = 2.6 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	
17:33	$P = 7.9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	37.8 mA, 2.95 A, 14.92 V
17:36	$P = 9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	37.3 mA, 2.93 A, 14.96 V
17:38	$P = 9.6 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	37.94 mA, 2.93 A, 15.05 V
Leak increase $\rightarrow$ 17:39	$P = 1.03 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	26.8 mA, 2.93 A, 15.07 V
17:47	$P = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	37.2 mA, 2.93 A, 15.14 V
17:51	$P = 1.07 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	37.8 mA, 2.93 A, 15.2 V
17:54	$P = 1.06 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	37.9 mA, 2.93 A, 15.21 V

041 XPS O 1s B 1s W 2P W 3P 0.5x0.5 @ 1100 eV $x=14, y=-13.3, z=17.3, R=30$

042 XPS BIS, LIS, NIS, OIS, W3P, VB @ 700 eV 1x1 slits same position as 041
 Sputter W(U) $x=5$ $y=-2$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$ 140 min
 2.62×10^{-4} mbar 500V, 4.5 mA, 500V Bias

Anneal W(U) w/e Beam 1 keV

Start $\Rightarrow$ 19:24 $P = 2.3 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.14 mA 0.0 A, 0.0 V
 19:25 $P = 8.6 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 36.6 mA, 2.95 A, 14.92 V
 19:27 $P = 9.6 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 37.6 mA, 2.93 A, 15.0 V
 19:30 $P = 1.08 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar 39.0 mA, 2.93 A, 15.1 V

AC heater resistance $\sim 10.6 \Omega$ unchanged

~~Continue XPS 043 heating~~ ~~start HV~~

043 XPS BIS, LIS, NIS, OIS, W3P VB @ 700 eV 1x1 slits same position as 041
 Start $\Rightarrow$ 20:07 (00:00:00 in MS)

close GV at Iteration 16, start leaking O_2

6×10^{-4} mbar at 17
 1.8×10^{-1} mbar at 18
 5×10^{-1} mbar at 19 (00:29:00 in MS) 4.2 bar gas monitor
 9.9×10^{-1} mbar at 21

Final 1 bar $\Rightarrow$ 22-71

[0:32:00 $\rightarrow$ 01:55:00]

Sputter W(U) $x=5$ $y=-2$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$ 140 min
 2.75×10^{-6} mbar 500V, 4.5 mA, 500V Bias 2.4 mA

Anneal W(U) w/e-Beam (1 keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$ 21:32 $P = 2.9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.13 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
 21:33 $P = 7 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 37.2 mA, 2.94 A, 14.85 V
 21:36 $P = 6.7 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 38.4 mA, 2.94 A, 15.0 V
 21:38 $P = 7.6 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 39 mA, 2.93 A, 15.07 V
 Leak Benzene $\rightarrow$ 21:40 $P = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 38.1 mA, 2.93 A, 15.14 V
 21:47 $P = 1.12 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 35.6 mA, 2.92 A, 15.14 V
 21:51 $P = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 36.1 mA, 2.92 A, 15.14 V
 21:55 $P = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 36.5 mA, 2.92 A, 15.14 V

Continue XPS 043: heating ramp to 100	T ($^{\circ}$ C)	Iteration	P (mbar)	Time (MMSS)	Power (V/A)
	137	85	1 mbar	02:18:00	5V 0.54A
stop heating, cool to RT	140	1385	1 mbar	03:50:00	0/0
close oxygen, go HV	115.9	146	0.8×10^{-6} mbar $\rightarrow$ 0	04:10:00	0/0
start HV	114.6	1501	2.2×10^{-7} mbar	04:18:00	0/0
	111	180	4.1×10^{-6} mbar	05:15:00	0/0
1 mbar, ramp up T to 200C	—	1813	1 mbar	05:20:00	7.4V/0.3A

Sputter W(U) $x=5$ $y=-2$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$ 140 min
 2.68×10^{-6} mbar 500V, 4.5 mA, 500V Bias

Anneal W(U) w/e-Beam (1 keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$ 00:07 $P = 3 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.08 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
 00:08 $P = 6.8 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 36.3 mA, 2.95 A, 14.85 V
 00:11 $P = 7.9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 38.93 mA, 2.93 A, 15.03 V
 00:13 $P = 7.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 38.4 mA, 2.92 A, 15.06 V

Continuing exp 043:

cool down to RT here

1 mbar not RT

T (°C)	Pressure (mbar)	P (mbar)	Time (min)	Power (V/A)
175.2	210	1	06:13:00	7.5 V / 1A
176.3	259	0.908	08:00:00	0 / 0
176.3				
112.6	285	0.94	08:56:00	0 / 0
109.8	334	1 mbar	11:01	0 / 0
109.8	337	HV	11:02	0 / 0
	366	END		

QMS data saved (RGA, ASCII)

XPS 044 700V survey, same spot

I_0 @ 1000 eV, 1.0 slits, 17.5 mA (OK)

XPS 045 Survey, hv = 1100 eV, 0.5 slits, old spot ($x=14, y=-13.3, z=17.3, R=30^\circ$), $f = 3.6 \times 10^{-8}$ new

Sputter W(U) $x=5, y=-2, z=3.8, \theta=315$ 140 mm, 2.4 μ A sample
 2.67×10^{-6} mbar, 500 V, 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

046 XPS BIS, OIS, W2P, W3P @ 1100 eV 0.5x0.5 slits, same spot 045

Anneal W(U) w/e-Beam (1 keV)

Start	Time	P (mbar)	Currents (mA)
Start	11:04	$P = 2.6 \times 10^{-9}$	0.15 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
	11:05	$P = 7.3 \times 10^{-9}$	36.78 mA, 2.94 A, 14.78 V
	11:08	$P = 6.3 \times 10^{-9}$	37.6 mA, 2.92 A, 14.92 V
	11:10	$P = 6.3 \times 10^{-9}$	38.7 mA, 2.92 A, 15.0 V

047 Survey 1100 0.5x0.5 slits. New spot $x=13.5, y=-13.45, z=17.5, R=30$

048 XPS BIS, OIS, W2P, W3P @ 1100 eV 0.5x0.5 slits same spot 047

049 Survey 700 1x1 slits same spot 048

LEED W(U) After 6 sputter anneals

24A 3 keV screen 0.7 keV MCP ($x=0, y=0, z=267, \theta=60$ center)

• 100 eV, 3.4 V wehmet, 120 V focus 70 V grid, (19 μ A, 0.93 μ A)

- center 0001
- $z+3$ 0002
- $z-3$ 0003
- $y-2.5$ 0004
- $y-4.5$ 0005
- $y-2.5, z+3$ 0006
- $y-2.5, z-3$ 0007

• 70 eV 2.0 V wehmet 80 V focus, 40 V grid, (19 μ A, 0.71 μ A)

- ~~center~~ $y-2.5$ 0001
- $z+3$ 0002
- $z-3$ 0003
- $y-5$ 0004
- $y+1$ 0005

050 XPS 700 eV BIS, CIS, NIS, OIS, W3P, VB 1.0x1.0 slits same spot as 049

Auger W(U) After 6 sputter anneals

241 A 3.4 V wehmet 0.15 keV screen 1600V focus 2 keV $\tau=15$ sens = 0.5 V, $\theta=90^\circ$

- $x=0, y=-2.5, z=267, \theta=60$ 0001/0002
- $x=0, y=-2.5, z=270, \theta=60$ 0003/0004
- $x=0, y=-2.5, z=265, \theta=60$ 0005/0006

051 XPS 700 eV BIS, CIS, NIS, OIS, W3P, VB 1x1 slits New spot $x=13.5, y=-13.45, z=16.2$ $R=30$

Rh - WBN Namomesh

052 survey @ 700 eV 1x1 slit X=13 y=-12.9 z=17.3 R=30 Rh 3d (372-38)

Sputter W(U) X=4 y=1 z=3.8 $\theta=315$ 140 min
 (7th cycle) 2.88×10^{-6} mbar 490 V, 4.6 mA, 510 V Bias 25 μ A sample

Anneal W(U) w/e-Beam (1 keV)
 start $\Rightarrow$ 16:50 P = 2.4×10^{-9} mbar 0.08 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
 16:51 P = 7.5×10^{-9} mbar 38 mA, 2.94 A, 14.79 V
 16:54 P = 7.6×10^{-9} mbar 38.2 mA, 2.92 A, 15.0 V
 16:55 P = 9×10^{-9} mbar 38.6 mA, 2.92 A, 15.07 V

053 XPS BIS, OIS, CIS, NIS, Rh 3d, VB @ 700 eV same spot as 052

054 XPS " " @ 700 eV X=14 y=-12.85 z=17.3 R=30

055 XPS " " @ 700 eV

close gate valve + start MS at start of scan

2.2×10^{-2} mbar at iteration 2

4×10^{-1} mbar at iteration 3

0.6×10^{-1} mbar at iteration 4 00:06:00 nms (39 bar in manifold)

Scan from 5-65 then close O₂ leak valve, open to turbo

Sputter W(U) X=4 y=1 z=3.8 $\theta=315$ 50 min
 2.7×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

Anneal W(U) w/e-beam (1 keV)
 start $\Rightarrow$ 18:52 P = 1.8×10^{-9} mbar 0.07, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
 18:54 P = 5.7×10^{-9} mbar 37.7 mA, 2.94 A, 14.78 V
 18:57 P = 5.5×10^{-9} mbar 38.28 mA, 2.92 A, 15.04 V
 19:00 P = 6.96×10^{-9} mbar 39.2 mA, 2.92 A, 15.07 V

Pressure rampdown at iteration 66 $\rightarrow$ HV at iteration 68 ok

Scan from 70-100

Sputter W(U) X=4 y=1 z=3.8 $\theta=315$ 140 min
 2.68×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.6 mA, 500 V bias

Scan 109 done turbo O₂ valve heating (2:50:00 nms)

T (K)	Iteration	P (mbar)	Time (nms)	Power (V/A)
109	111	0.98 0.98	2:50:00	4.3 V / 0.4 A
118.8	116	1	3:02:00	3.7 V / 0.5 A
121	175	0.95	4:45:00	3.08 / 0.29 A
cooling $\downarrow$ 110.5	201	HV	5:25:00	0 / 0
109.96	201 30	NV	6:28:00	0 / 0

Anneal W(U) w/e-Beam (1 keV)
 start $\Rightarrow$ 20:49 P = 2.3×10^{-9} mbar 0.15 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
 20:50 P = 5.6×10^{-9} mbar 38.3 mA, 2.94 A, 14.85 V
 20:54 P = 5.6×10^{-9} mbar 38.7 mA, 2.92 A, 14.99 V
 20:57 P = 6.2×10^{-9} mbar 37.6 mA, 2.91 A, 15.01 V
 21:00 P = 7.6×10^{-9} mbar 38.3 mA, 2.91 A, 15.07 V

Sputter W(U) X=4 y=1 z=3.8 $\theta=315$ 40 min
 3.0×10^{-6} mbar 400 V, 4.6 mA, 510 V Bias

Anneal W(U) w/e-Beam (1 keV)

Start	⇒ 22:55	P = 2×10^{-9} mbar	0.15 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
	22:56	P = 6×10^{-9} mbar	38.9 mA, 14.98V, 2.94A
	22:59	P = 4.8×10^{-9} mbar	39.3 mA, 15.06V, 2.92A
	23:01	P = 5.2×10^{-9} mbar	38.54 mA, 15.05V, 2.91A
	23:05	P = 7.3×10^{-9} mbar	38.3 mA, 15.07V, 2.91A
	23:09	P = 1.0×10^{-8} mbar	39.1 mA, 15.1V, 2.91A

LEED W(U) After 10th cycle

- 2.4 A, 3kV screen, 0.7 keV MCP (x=0 y=-3 z=267 θ=60 ~center)
- 100 eV, 3.4 V Wehnelt, 120 V focus, 70 V grid (19 μA, 0.94 μA)
 - center 0001
 - z+3 0002/0003
 - z-3 0004
 - 70 eV, 2.0 V Wehnelt, 84 V focus, 49 V grid, (19 μA, 0.73 μA)
 - z-3
 - center
 - z+3

Sputter W(U) x=4 y=-2 z=38 θ=815 120 min
 3.2×10^{-6} mbar 400 V, 4.6 mA, 510 V bias

Backfilling 1 mbar O₂, cooling XPS; move to 100 C

Temp (C)	Pressure (mbar)	P (mbar)	Time (MMSS)	Power
110	232	1	6:33:00	5V / 0.54A
138.5	241	1	6:50:00	5.1V / 0.53A
140	300	1	8:54:00	4.97 / 0.534 → 0/0
111.7	3206	0.94 → HV	9:45:00	0/0
	3505	HV	10:30:00	0/0

multiple reactions! → STOP

Anneal W(U) w/e-Beam (1 keV)

Start	⇒ 00:40	P = 1.7×10^{-9} mbar	0.15 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
	00:41	P = 5.6×10^{-9} mbar	40.3 mA, 15.0V, 2.94A
	00:46	P = 8.0×10^{-9} mbar	41.2 mA, 15.1V, 2.93A

LEED Cu(111) After +1 cycle

2.4 A filament, 3kV screen, 0.7 keV MCP - "star" mapping
 ↳ 100 eV
 ↳ 70 eV
 not completely clean yet!

056 XPS Survey 700 eV, 19x, some spot

057 XPS B1s, O1s, C1s, N1s, Rh3d, VB @ 700 eV, some spot HV: 30x

Move: x=14, y=-12.85, z=18.6, P=30

058 XPS Survey 700 eV, 10x

059 XPS B1s, O1s, C1s, N1s, Rh3d, VB @ 700 eV, P = 1.9×10^{-8} mbar

I₀ @ 1000 eV, 1.0 dil = 17.23 μA (0x)

Ca(III) XPS 060 Survey 700 eV, 1.9×10^{-8} mbar, $x=13$, $y=-11.3$, $z=17.3$, $R=30^\circ$ #15 iterations
 700 eV, 1.0 slits (see opt we had during O₂ anneal)

XPS 061 700 eV: Cu 3p, O 1s, Bi 2s, Ni 2s, Cl 2s, VB, same position as 060 $r=1.8 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar
 Sputter W(LM) $x=4$ $y=+2$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$ 120 min
 2.7×10^{-6} mbar 500 V 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

Gr-W sample

062 Survey Survey 700 eV, 1x1 slits $x=14$ $y=-13.4$ $z=17.3$ $R=30$

063 Cu 3p, O 1s, Bi 2s, Ni 2s, Cl 2s, VB @ 700 eV, same position as 062

Anneal W(LM)	w/e-Beam (1 keV)		
Start $\Rightarrow$ 10:44	$P=1.5 \times 10^{-9}$	0.1 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V	
$\Rightarrow$ 10:45	$P=1.2 \times 10^{-8}$	37.9 mA, 2.93 A, 14.78 V	
10:47	$P=4.6 \times 10^{-9}$	41.8 mA, 2.93 A, 15.14 V	
10:50	$P=5.2 \times 10^{-9}$	42.35 mA, 2.93 A, 15.24 V	

064 Survey 1100 eV 0.5x0.5 ~~opt~~ same spot as 063

065 XPS Cl 2s, Bi 2s, O 1s, W 3p, W 2p @ 1100 same spot as 064

Sputter (13th) W(LM) $x=4$ $y=2$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$ 20 min
 2.6×10^{-6} mbar 510 V, 4.6 mA, 500 V bias 2.4 μ A sample

Anneal W(LM)	w/e-Beam (1 keV)		
Start $\Rightarrow$ 12:40	$P=1.7 \times 10^{-9}$	0.1 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V	
12:41	$P=4.2 \times 10^{-9}$	38.2 mA, 2.93 A, 14.92 V	
12:44	$P=5.09 \times 10^{-9}$	41.5 mA, 2.93 A, 15.14 V	
12:48	$P=6.3 \times 10^{-9}$	42.9 mA, 2.93 A, 15.29 V	

Sputter W(LM) $x=4$ $y=4$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$ 20 min
 3.03×10^{-6} mbar 490 V, 4.0 mA, 510 V bias 2.6 μ A sample

Anneal W(LM)	w/e-Beam (1 keV)		
Start $\Rightarrow$ 14:02	$P=1.9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	0.1 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V	
14:03	$P=4.2 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	38.5 mA, 2.93 A, 14.85 V	
14:07	$P=5.7 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	42.4 mA, 2.93 A, 15.24 V	

066 XPS Cl 2s, Bi 2s, O 1s, W 3p W 2p @ 1100 eV $x=15$ $y=-13.3$ $z=17.3$ $R=30$

LEIS W(LM) After 14 Sputter Anneals
 24 A 3kV screen 0.7 keV MCP ($x=20$ $y=-4$ $z=26.7$ $\theta=60$ ~ center)
 • 100 eV, 3.4 V wehmet, 120 V, 70 V, (18 μ A, 0.9 μ A)
 - center
 - $z+3$
 - $z-3$
 • 70 eV, 2.0 V wehmet, 84 V focus, 49 V grid, (18 μ A, 0.7 μ A)
 - $z-3$
 - center
 - $z+3$

067 XPS Cl 2s, Bi 2s, O 1s, Ni 2s, W 3p, VB @ 700 eV 1x1 slits same spot as 066

Sputter W(LM) $x=4$ $y=4$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$ 20 min
 2.6×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.6 mA, 500 V Bias

068 XPS @ IS, US, NB, W3P @ 700 eV 1x1 slits same spot as 067
 Start MS at start of scan

Anneal W(M) w/e-Beam (1keV)

start => 16:12	P = 2.03 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	0.09 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0V
16:13	P = 4.6 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	38.8 mA, 2.93A, 14.85V
16:16	P = 3.9 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	41.6 mA, 2.93A, 15.14V
16:18	P = 5.1 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	42.7 mA, 2.93A, 15.23V
16:20	P = 1.18 x 10 ⁻⁶ mbar	36.5 mA, 2.91A, 15.14V
16:23	P = 1.14 x 10 ⁻⁶ mbar	36.7 mA, 2.91A, 15.17V
16:33	P = 1.13 x 10 ⁻⁶ mbar	37.6 mA, 2.91A, 15.25V

Leak Benzene ->

Closed GV at Iteration 15

2.1 x 10 ⁻³ mbar	17
7.0 x 10 ⁻² mbar	18
8.1 x 10 ⁻¹ mbar	20

Scan from 21 - 33 at 1 mbar O₂, RT

LEED W(M) After 15 sputter anneals + Benzene exposure
 2.4A, 3 keV screen, 0.7 keV MCP (x=0 y=-4 z=267 θ=90)
 • 100 eV, 3.4V wehnelt, 120V focus, 70V grid (19 μA, 0.9 μA)
 - center
 - center higher exposure time
 - z+3
 - z-3
 • 70 eV 2.0V wehnelt, 84V focus, 47V grid (19 μA, 0.7 μA)
 - z-3
 - center
 - z+3

Closed LV at 84 open GV at 89

1.9 x 10 ⁻⁷ mbar	at 92
9.2 x 10 ⁻⁸ mbar	at 96

Scan from 96 - 135 at RT, UVV

Closed GV at 136; 1 mbar at 138 start holey

T (K)	Heater	P (mbar)	Time (min)	Power (V/A)
109.6	139	0.98	2:55:00	4.98 / 0.46
119.78	142.5	0.97	3:03:00	3.41 / 0.31
121	142.5 210	0.98	4:35:00	0 / 0
111.2	142.5 230	0.98 HV	5:05:00	0 / 0
71	275 - 278	HV - 1 mbar	6:10:00	6 / 0.55

Argon W(M) After 15 sputter anneals + Benzene exposure
 2.41A, 3.4V wehnelt, 0.15 keV screen, 1600V focus 2keV E=15 sens=0.5
 - x=0 y=-4 z=267 θ=60 (center) 0001/0002
 - z=265 (Bottom) 0003/0004

Sputter W(M) x=4 y=4 z=3.8 θ=315 20 min
 2.82 x 10⁻⁶ mbar 500V, 4.6 mA, 500V B.O.S 2.6 μA Sample

Anneal W(M) w/e-Beam (1keV)

Start => 19:54	P = 2.7 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	0.09 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0V
19:55	P = 6.5 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	37.8 mA, 2.94A, 14.92V
19:59	P = 8.3 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	42 mA, 2.93A, 15.21V
20:04	P = 1 x 10 ⁻⁸ mbar	43.0 mA, 2.92A, 15.3 V

Sputter $w(\mu)$ $x=4$ $y=4$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=60$ 20 min
 2.7×10^{-8} mbar 500V, 4.6mA, 500V Bias

Anneal $w(\mu)$ w/e-Beam (1keV)
 Start $\Rightarrow$ 21:16 $P = 2.3 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.08 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
 21:17 $P = 5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 38.26 mA, 2.92V, 14.85
 21:21 $P = 7 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 42.75 mA 2.92V, 15.29V

Sputter $w(\mu)$ $x=4$ $y=4$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=60$ 20 min
 2.75×10^{-6} mbar 500V, 4.6 mA 500 V Bias 2.6 μ A Sample

Continuing XPS; heating to 100C

	T (C)	Iteration	P (mbar)	Time (mm:ss)	Power (V/A)
	138.5	296	1.1	6:40:00	5.2 / 0.54
cooldown $\downarrow$	139.95	355	0.97	8:24:00	5.12 / 0.536
	113	375	0.93 $\rightarrow$ HV	8:56:00	0/0
		380	HV		
		425	HV		

Anneal $w(\mu)$ w/e-Beam heater (1keV)
 Start $\Rightarrow$ 22:36 $P = 2.2 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.08 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
 22:37 $P = 4.4 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 38.68 mA, 14.85V, 2.92A
 22:40 $P = 5.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 42.0 mA 15.06V, 2.92A
 22:42 $P = 6.7 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 42.7 mA 15.2V, 2.92A
 leak Borazine $\rightarrow$ 22:44 $P = 1.2 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 38.7 mA, 15.21V, 2.91A
 22:46 $P = 1.5 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 37.9 mA, 15.25V, 2.91A
 22:50 $P = 1.5 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 38.04 mA, 15.29V, 2.91A
 22:54 $P = 1.48 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 38.5 mA, 15.31V, 2.91A
 22:58 $P = 1.46 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 39.1 mA, 15.36V, 2.91A

LEED After 18 (wow!) Sputter-Anneals + Borazine

2.4A, 3kV screen, 0.7kV MCP, $x=0$ $y=4$ $z=2.67$ $\theta=60$ (center)
 • 100 eV 3.4 eV wheel + 120V focus, 70V grid (19mA, 0.73A)
 = center 0001
 - $z+3$ 0002
 = $z-3$ 0003
 • 70 eV 2.0 eV wheel + 84V focus 49V grid (19mA, 0.73A)
 = $z-3$
 - center
 - $z+3$

Continuing XPS; heating to 150C

	T (C)	Iteration	P (mbar)	Time (mm:ss)	Power (V/A)
heating $\downarrow$	110	427	HV $\rightarrow$ 0.99	10:35:00	6.5 / 0.75A
	155	456	0.98	11:12:00	6.05 / 0.78
cooling $\downarrow$	158.5	515	0.97	13:41:00	0/0
	114	530	HV	15:18:00	0/0
		570			

Annealing Av-nca in pizza oven: T=500C [1A, 24.16V] for 15 min +

069 XPS Snowy, same position as 068

Machine development shift, but the beam seems OK

XPS 070 New spot (HV after 150°C O₂ anneal) x=15, y=-13.3, z=16.3, R=30°
 Cu₃P, O_{1s}, Cl_{2s}, VB

Am-nica #2 x=12, y=-11.3, z=36, R=30°

XPS 071 Am 4p @ 700eV, 1.0 slits E_F=20eV

XPS 072 Am 4p @ 1100eV, ~~0.5~~ 0.5 slits, E_F=20eV

TEST: 2nd order: 1st v1 = 1100eV, 1.0 slits

XPS 073 550eV - 2200eV E_K window, E_F=100eV

IA 24⁺: decaying beam

RBN foil taken out

Cu(III) measured with decaying beam @ 700eV, 1.0 slits, x=13, y=-11.3, z=17.3, R=30°

1st	I ₀ = 280 mA	Survey, Cu ₃ P, O _{1s} , Bi _{1s} , Ni _{2s} , Cl _{2s} , VB
2	I ₀ = 277 mA	XPS 075
3	271 mA	
4	I ₀ = 267 mA	
6	I ₀ = 260 mA	
9	I ₀ = 211 mA	
10	183 mA	
12	178 mA	
14	175 mA	
16	0 mA	(big beam loss)

LEED Am-nica #2 25A, W=3.4V, I_F=19 mA, I_B=0.92 mA, MCP=700V, 100eV
 ↳ no LEED pattern; no pic saved [O₁] but looks same everywhere.

Am-nica #2: annealing to 520°C, p_{max}=2.6x10⁻⁸ mbar, then @ 500°C for 30'

LEED - no pattern again, sides of spot depending

• Co foil: cutting, sonicating in ethanol, then in MilliQ (both 15 min), then UV cleaning from

Am-nica #2, YAG, ~~TC~~ TC sample plate, RBN-Cu foil taken out

• 5x1 Co foil in, 5x1 Am-nica #3 in.

Sputter W(U) out 400°C x=4, y=4, z=3.8, θ=315 30 min
 2.9x10⁻⁶ mbar 490 V, 4.6 mA, 510V BIAS 2.4 μA sample
 T=397°C 16.14 V, 2.105 A
 T=408.1°C 16.08 V, 2.104 A
 shut down filament after 30 min, but keep sputtering
 T=408.1°C 0.0 V, 0.0 A 19:45
 T=135°C stop sputtering at 20:05 30 min while cooling

Annealing Au-nica sample #3 at ~~250°C~~ 250°C with slow ramp (no dwell at 250)
 ↳ p ~ 10⁻⁷, short spikes at 10⁻⁶

Anneal W(U) w/eBeam (1keV)

start	20:09	P = 2.8x10 ⁻⁹ mbar	0.03 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0V
	20:10	P = 7.1x10 ⁻⁹ mbar	29.6 mA, 2.94 A, 15.07
	20:13	P = 7.1x10 ⁻⁹ mbar	39.5 mA, 2.91 A, 15.08
	20:15	P = 7.1x10 ⁻⁹ mbar	41.5 mA, 2.91 A, 15.21

Sputtering Co-sample: 5x ~~20~~ 20m, P_{Ar} = 2.45 · 10⁻⁶ mbar, 4.5 A discharge, 1kV bias
 ↳ h = 3.8, 3.3, 2.8, 2.3, 1.8, 1.3, 0.8, ~~0.3~~

Annealing Au-nica #3 to ~~430~~ 430°C; dwell from 9:30 pm to 11:30 pm, then slow cool down
 ↳ p ~ 10⁻⁸

Co sample moved to ATC, Au to PC → ! Visible mark on Au ~ over border!

10.6.2020 Co foil

AC: $I_{Co} = 1100 \text{ nbar}$, $I_{AC1} = 3.6 \times 10^{-8} \text{ nbar}$, $I_{PRE} = 7.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ nbar}$, $I_{MS} = 7.3 \times 10^{-9} \text{ nbar}$, $I_{AC2} = 4R$,
 PC: $I_{IC} = 8.2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ nbar}$, $I_{PRE} = 1.73 \times 10^{-2} \text{ nbar}$ Analyser: All UR except 2nd: $p = 5.7 \times 10^{-9} \text{ nbar}$, $SCPM = 1.2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ nbar}$

$J_0 = 17.1 \mu A$ @ 1.0 slits, 1000 eV

XPS-076 Survey 1000 eV (Co foil), 1000 eV, 1.0 slits, $X=13$, $Y=-11.05$, $Z=46$, $R=30^\circ$ x10
 078 O_{1s} , Co $2p$ @ 1000 eV, one spot ($p = 3.4 \times 10^{-8} \text{ nbar}$) x30
 XPS 079 Survey @ 700 eV, 1.0 slits, same spot x10
 080 O_{1s} , Cl_{1s} , VB @ 700 eV ($p = 3.2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ nbar}$) x30

LEED Au-mica #3: Most of the annealed area shows no LEED (just diffuse BG), 100 eV, stable LEED

[XAS00] Co L-edge AEX, one position

[XAS01] - repeat of [XAS01]

[XAS02] - slightly corrected, status unknown

[XAS03], [XAS04] - same settings as [XAS03]

Settings: Energy range

765 - 771	1 eV
771 - 788	0.25 eV
788 - 791	0.5 eV
791 - 800	0.25 eV
800 - 805	1 eV

[XAS05]: $Z=47$

[XAS06]: $Z=45$

[XAS07] Try O k-edge $E_{center} = 508 \text{ eV}$ } $Z=45$

[XAS08] O k-edge, $E_{center} = 500 \text{ eV}$

[XAS09] O k-edge, $E_{center} = 500 \text{ eV}$, $Z=46$

[XAS10] O k-edge, $E_{center} = 500 \text{ eV}$, $Z=46$, 20.12 -

Co L-edge $\rightarrow$ $E_p = 100 \text{ V}$
 $E_{center} = 772 \text{ eV}$
 T.H.PPHAXPES
 Acquisition: Fixed
 Energy: Kinetic
 Detector: APC
 Element: H:PPHAXPES

Slits 1
 Time 1.00
 Size 0.25
 IWR 1

O k-edge $E_{center} = 500 \text{ eV}$

Sputter $w(M)$ at $400^\circ C$ $X=4$ $Y=4$ $Z=38$ $\Theta=315$

$2.64 \times 10^{-6} \text{ nbar}$ 500 V 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

$T = 364.6^\circ C$ 16.15 V 2.104 A 12:50

$T = 366^\circ C$ 16.14 V 2.104 A 13:10

$T = 376.4^\circ C$ 16.11 V 2.104 A 13:40 shut off heating

$T = 103.8^\circ C$ 0.00 V 0.0 A 14:10

2.5 μA
 sample

Anneal $w(M)$ w/e-Beam heater (1 keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$ 14:12 $P = 2 \times 10^{-9} \text{ nbar}$ 0.08 mA, 0.0 V, 0.0 A

14:13 $P = 6 \times 10^{-9} \text{ nbar}$ 37.28 mA, 14.85 V, 2.90 A

14:16 $P = 4.4 \times 10^{-9} \text{ nbar}$ 37.9 mA, 2.89 A, 15.00 V

14:20 $P = 5.3 \times 10^{-9} \text{ nbar}$ 38.7 mA, 2.89 A, 15.07 V

Sputter 21st $w(M)$ @ RT $X=0$ $Y=0$ $Z=38$ $\Theta=315$

$2.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ nbar}$ 510 V, 4.5 mA, 490 V Bias

Anneal $w(M)$ w/e-Beam heater (1 keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$ 15:46 $P = 1.7 \times 10^{-9}$ 0.08 mA, 0.0 V, 0.0 A

15:47 $P = 4.3 \times 10^{-9}$ 35.8 mA, 14.78 V, 2.9 A

15:51 $P = 4.3 \times 10^{-9}$ 40.0 mA, 15.09 V, 2.9 A

LEED $w(M)$ after 21 sputter - Anneals

2.4 A, 3.4 kV ~~screen~~ screen 0.4 μ MCP $X=0$ $Y=4$ $Z=367$ $\Theta=260$

• 100 eV 3.4 eV 120 V focus, 70 V grid (20 mA, 0.94 μ A)

- Center

- $Z+3$

- $Z-3$

• 70 eV 2.0 eV Hel focus, 49 eV grid

Sputter $w(M)$ $X=0$ $Y=0$ $Z=38$ $\Theta=315$

$2.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ nbar}$ 500 V 4.6 mA 500 V Bias

- [XAS 12] Co L-edge ^{Keithley connected, not sure it is grounded. Measuring sample current (TEY)}
- [XAS 13] O K-edge ^{Keithley connected, not sure it is grounded.}
- [XAS 14] O K-edge - repeat of 13
- [XAS 15] O K-edge - repeat of 13
- [XAS 16] O K-edge - Poll 0.5 sec

Poll 1 sec
Poll Curr slow

Keithley: still connection error -213

- 6517A Poll 1 sec poll curr slow N AVG = 10
- XAS 17 ~~not used~~ XAS 18 using POL 0.1 with 100 ms delay.
- [XAS 19] O K-edge, now using N AVG = 10 (not 1)

- [XAS 20] O K-edge, using Bins of -20V
- [XAS 21] O K-edge, using Bins of -15V

! Learned if you apply Bins for TEY, you have to change the Ecenter for AEX

- ✓ [XAS 22] O K-edge, Bins = 0, Ecenter, AEX = 500 eV
 - X [XAS 23] O K-edge Bins = -5V, Ecenter, AEX = 495 eV
 - X [XAS 24] O K-edge Bins = -10V, Ecenter, AEX = 490 eV
- Bins ↓ ⇒ Center ↑

- [XAS 25] O K-edge Bins = -10V, Ecenter = 510 eV
- [XAS 26] O K-edge Bins = -5V, Ecenter = 505 eV
- [XAS 27] O K-edge Bins = -15V, Ecenter = 515 eV
- [XAS 28] O K-edge Bins = -20V, Ecenter = 520 eV
- [XAS 29] O K-edge Bins = +5V, Ecenter = 495 eV
- [XAS 30] O K-edge, Bins = +10V, Ecenter = 490 eV
- [XAS 31] O K-edge, Bins = +15V, Ecenter = 485 eV
- [XAS 32] O K-edge, Bins = +20V, Ecenter = 480 eV

- X [XAS 33] Co L-edge, Bins = 0V, Ecenter = 772 eV Overflow → Alarmed

- [XAS 34] Co L-edge, Bins = 0V, Ecenter = 772 eV
- [XAS 35] Co L-edge Bins = -5V, Ecenter = 777 eV
- [XAS 36] Co L-edge Bins = -10V, Ecenter = 782 eV
- [XAS 37] Co L-edge Bins = +5V, Ecenter = 787 eV
- [XAS 38] Co L-edge Bins = -20V, Ecenter = 792 eV
- [XAS 39] Co L-edge Bins = -20V, AEX measured in Sweep Mode T_{int} 0.04, BE 220-240 eV

Scintia Panel: E_p = 100 Acq: Sweep Slits 1
Low = 220 eV Energy: Binding T_{int} 0.04 s
High = 240 eV Detector: ADC Iter 1

- [XAS 42] Co L-edge Bins = 0V, AEX in Sweep mode ↑
- [XAS 43] Co L-edge Bins = +20V, AEX in Sweep mode ↑
- [XAS 44] Co L-edge Bins = +10V, AEX in Sweep mode
- [XAS 45] Co L-edge Bins = -10V, AEX in Sweep mode
- [XAS 47] O K-edge Bins 0V, AEX Sweep
- [XAS 48] O K-edge Bins 10V, AEX sweep mode
- [XAS 49] O K-edge Bins -10V, AEX sweep
- [XAS 50] O K-edge Bins -20V, AEX sweep
- [XAS 51] O K-edge Bins 20V, AEX sweep
- [XAS 52] O K-edge Bins 20V, AEX sweep (repeat 1)
- [XAS 53] O K-edge Bins -20V, AEX sweep (repeat)
- [XAS 54] O K-edge Bins -10V, AEX sweep (repeat)
- [XAS 55] O K-edge Bins 10V, AEX sweep (repeat)
- [XAS 56] O K-edge Bins 0V, AEX sweep (repeat)

Mass spec: Analy Scan (2020-06-10 before H₂O leak)

Close gate valve, ~~close~~ GAS BALLAST ~~close~~ OPEN, dead valve analyzer

Leak ~1.1 mbar H₂O, Analy Scan (2020-06-10 after H₂O leak)

[XAS 57]	Ca	L-edge	Bias -20V	ABY sweep	
[XAS 58]	Ca	L-edge	Bias -10V	ABY sweep	
[XAS 59]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 0V	ABY sweep	← pressure higher partway here, 1.4 mbar
[XAS 60]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 10V	ABY sweep	
[XAS 61]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 20V	ABY sweep	
[XAS 62]	O	K-edge	Bias -20V	ABY sweep	← pressure high (1.5 mbar) ⇒ "test"
[XAS 63]	O	K-edge	Bias -10V	ABY sweep	→ reflect, to make sure the p effect (Tilt off different view)
[XAS 64]	O	K-edge	Bias -10V	ABY sweep	
[XAS 65]	O	K-edge	Bias 0V	ABY sweep	adjusted valve: ↓ drops!
[XAS 66]	O	K-edge	Bias 0V	ABY sweep	

General note: adjusting pressure during measurement causes drop/spike in signal
 ⇒ increase P before scan - 10 decrease slowly = background steady increase.

[XAS 67]	O	K-edge	Bias 10V	ABY sweep
[XAS 68]	O	K-edge	Bias 20V	ABY sweep
[XAS 69]	Ca	L-edge	Bias -20V	ABY sweep
[XAS 70]	Ca	L-edge	Bias -10V	ABY sweep
[XAS 71]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 0V	ABY sweep
[XAS 72]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 10V	ABY sweep
[XAS 73]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 20V	ABY sweep
[XAS 74]	O	K-edge	Bias -20V	ABY sweep
[XAS 75]	O	K-edge	Bias -10V	ABY sweep
[XAS 76]	O	K-edge	Bias 0V	ABY sweep
[XAS 77]	O	K-edge	Bias 10V	ABY sweep
[XAS 78]	O	K-edge	Bias 20V	ABY sweep
[XAS 79]	Ca	L-edge	Bias -20V	ABY sweep
[XAS 80]	Ca	L-edge	Bias -10V	ABY sweep
[XAS 81]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 0	ABY sweep
[XAS 82]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 0	ABY sweep

Time	Pressure
5:28:00	1.1 mbar → 5:37:30
5:41:00	1.2 mbar → 5:52
6:01:00	1.1 mbar → 6:17:30
6:20:00	1.2 mbar → 6:35
6:41	1.1 mbar → 6:56
7:02:30	1.1 mbar → 7:18:00

grip on all-metal valve loosely/moving? Lucky spot found, stable pressure

[XAS 83]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 10	ABY sweep	7:21 1.1 mbar → 7:37 1.1 mbar
[XAS 84]	Ca	L-edge	Bias 20	ABY sweep	7:41 1.1 mbar → 7:57 1.1 mbar
[XAS 85]	O	K-edge	Bias -20	ABY sweep	7:59 1.1 mbar → 8:13 1.1 mbar
[XAS 86]	O	K-edge	Bias -10	ABY sweep	8:15 1.1 mbar → 1.1 mbar
[XAS 87]	O	K-edge	0	ABY sweep	
[XAS 88]	O	K-edge	+10		1.1 mbar
[XAS 89]	O	K-edge	+20		1.1 mbar

Sample bias → 0

XPS 084 Survey 10000V @ 1.1 mbar H₂O x=13, y=-11.05, z=46, p=30
 XPS 085 Cl 0, Bias 0V
 XPS 086 Cl 0, Bias +10V ! Bias does not work :-C

XPS 087 K1s Bias re-stated

XPS 088 Cls Bias -10V (now it works), Light ON on key kindly!

Scan 1-5: Bias = -10V
6-10: Bias = +10V
11-15: Bias = 0V
16-20: Bias = -10V

∇ If light is off, there is no Bias applied.
o You have to switch it OFF → ON to make it work
↑
In EPICS

XPS 90 o K-edge at Bias = ~~0V~~ @ 1.1 nbar ∇ Trust these data
-10V (Len)

XPS 91 o K-edge at Bias = 0V @ 1.1 nbar (Changes current sharply @ -0.57V Bias)
XPS 92 Co L-edge at Bias = 0V @ 1.1 nbar Seems to be due to secondary electrons!

XPS 93 Co L-edge at Bias = -10V @ 1.1 nbar

XPS 94 Co L-edge at Bias = -20V @ 1.1 nbar

XPS 95 o K-edge @ Bias = -20V @ 1.1 nbar

XPS 96 o K-edge with Bias = -1V, E_{cal} = 499V kinetic Fixed
(Testing if I measured/set O K-edge AEX regions correctly using known Fixed settings)

XPS 90 1020eV Cls, Cu 2p, O1s

Attaching H₂ to PC. Flashing gas lines 1x. ACP15 with GB closed. When f_{PC,PRE} < 10 nbar, opening GB. This helped a lot to get the H₂ out of the pump.

- o Am-nica #3 moved to AC → out ; ~~Am-nica #3~~
- o Co foil left in LLC

Anneal W(M) in H₂ w/ e Beam heater

Start	Time	P	mA	A	V
	15:19	$P = 2.1 \times 10^{-7}$ (H ₂)	0.1 mA	0.0 A	0.0 V
	15:20	$P = 2.2 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	37.5 mA	2.9 A	14.78 V
	15:23	$P = 2.2 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	38.9 mA	2.9 A	15.00 V
	15:27	$P = 2.2 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	38.07 mA	2.89 A	15.07 V
	15:32	$P = 2.2 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	38.5 mA	2.88 A	15.1 V
	15:38	$P = 2.2 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	37.7 mA	2.87 A	15.07 V
	15:40	$P = 2.2 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	37.6 mA	2.87 A	15.07

LEED W(M) After 2d₀₀₁ sputter / Anneal in H₂ ~800°C
2.4A, 3 kW Screen, 0.7 kV MCP (X=0 y=-4 z=267 θ=60 center)
• 100 eV 3.4 eV, 120V focus, 20 V grid, (17 μA, 0.89 μA)
- center 0001
- z+3 0002
- z-3 0003
• 70 eV 2.04, 84 V focus, 49 V grid (17 μA, 0.7 μA)
- z-3 0004
- center 0005
- z+3 0006

AC vented, 300 μm cone attached.

Am-nica #3 out
Am-nica #4 in
Cu single crystal (indium) inserted

Outgassing KAN 0.1m in exicator (offsite)

Annealing Au-mica sample #4 (?) : ~3300C for 1h ($p < 10^{-9}$ or less)

↳ LEED: 100eV largely only background, faint spots in tiny areas only
by eye no distinct feature on surface [saved: LEED/2020_06_11 Au-mica.tif]

Annealing Au-mica #4 ~400C x 1h [2.4A filament, 2V Wehn, 1.18 μ A current] 330C anneal

↳ LEED [/2020_06_11 Au-mica 400C anneal 1h] 100eV
↳ as before, only faint spots visible in some areas

Anneal (flash) Au-mica #4 to ~500C ~~some settling~~

↳ LEED [/2020_06_11 Au-mica 500C flash] some settling

↳ Likely substrate-Au interface problem! ↳ spots again only in small areas, mostly disordered

Analyzer: Outgassing MCF to 1630V, Screen to 3660V

$R_x = +0.4142$ $R_y = -0.125$ $I_0 = 17 \mu A$

[XAS98] Co foil: Co L-edge swept, Bias = -20V, $\mu = 3.6 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar // Binding, 220-240

[XAS99] Co foil: O K-edge swept, Bias = -20V, $\mu = 3.5 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar // Binding, 60-75

[XAS100] Co foil, O K-edge @ 5.0 mbar H_2O , Bias = -20V ($\mu_i = 4.9$ mbar, $\mu_{end} = 4.7$ mbar)

[XAS101] Co foil, Co L-edge @ 4.7 mbar H_2O , Bias = -20V ($\mu_i = 4.7$ mbar, $\mu_{end} = 4.6$ mbar)

[XAS102] Co foil, Co L-edge @ 12 mbar H_2O , Bias = -20V ($\mu_i = 12$ mbar, $\mu_{end} =$ mbar)

↳ TEV $\propto$ proportional to the pressure AEV part of read ($\mu_i = 12$ mbar, started changing, now $\mu = 8.9$ mbar, then increased to 15 mbar)

[XAS103] Co foil, O K-edge @ 13 mbar H_2O , Bias = -20V ($\mu_i = 13$ mbar, dropping; $\mu_{end} =$

↳ I_0 seems to follow pressure

[XAS104] Co foil, O K-edge @ 9.4 mbar, Bias = -30V ($\mu_i = 9.4$ mbar, $\mu_{end} = 14$ mbar, continuously increasing)

[XAS105] Co foil, Co L-edge @ 14 mbar, Bias = -30V ($\mu_i = 14$ mbar, $\mu_{end} = 16$ mbar, only increasing)

[XAS106] Co foil, Co L-edge @ 16 mbar, Bias = -20V ($\mu_i = 16$ mbar, $\mu_{end} = 17$ mbar)

[XAS107] Co foil, Co L-edge @ 17 mbar, Bias = -40V ($\mu_i = 17$ mbar, $\mu_{end} =$

Anneal $W(U)$ in H_2 w/e-Beam heater

start	⇒ 11:56	$P = 4.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	0.08 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
	12:01	$P = 5.6 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar (H_2)	0.4 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
	12:03	$P = 5.67 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	37.2 mA, 14.7V, 2.9A
	12:07	$P = 5.7 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	37.7 mA, 15.0V, 2.88A
	12:11	$P = 5.75 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	38.6 mA, 15.09V, 2.88A
	12:16	$P = 5.78 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	37.6 mA, 15.07V, 2.87A
	12:23	$P = 5.8 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	38.6 mA, 15.13V, 2.87A

Anneal $W(U)$ in H_2 w/e-Beam heater

start	⇒ 13:50	$P = 5.8 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	0.15 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
	13:53	$P = 2.04 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar (H_2)	0.15 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
	13:55	$P = 2.15 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	38.4 mA, 14.85V, 2.9A
	13:59	$P = 2.12 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	36.9 mA, 15.0V, 2.87A
	14:08	$P = 1.91 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	38.7 mA, 15.14V, 2.87A
	14:12	$P = 1.93 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	37.4 mA, 15.07V, 2.86A
	14:20	$P = 1.95 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	38.6 mA, 15.07V, 2.86A

[XAS108] Co foil, O k-edge @ 17 eV (stable), Bias = -30V

[XAS109] Co foil, Co L-edge @ 17 eV (stable), Bias = -30V

PC: massive buildup due to H₂. Solved by opening GB on APC15.

LEED WLM) After 3rd H₂ anneal

2.4 A, 3kV screen, 0.7 MCP (x=0 y=-2 z=267 θ=60 ~ center)

• 100eV 3.4V wehnelt, 120V focus, 70V grid (18μA, 0.89μA)

- center 0001
- z+3 0002
- z-3 0003

• 70 eV 2.0V wehnelt 84V focus, 491V grid (

- z-3 0004
- center 0005
- z+3 0006
- Back (z=259) 0007

Anneal in H₂ w/ eBeam heater

Start => 15:27	P = 6x10 ⁻¹⁰ mbar	0.08 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
15:28	P = 8.45x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	0.14 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
15:32	P = 8.56x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	39.5 mA, 14.92V, 2.9A
15:37	P = 8.5x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	38.1 mA, 15.07V, 2.87A
15:43	P = 8.0x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	37.7 mA, 15.07V, 2.86A
15:51	P = 8.49x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	39.4 mA, 15.12V, 2.86A

Anneal in H₂ w/ eBeam heater

Start => 16:26	P = 8.2x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	0.39 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
16:28	P = 8.16x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	39.2 mA, 14.93V, 2.89A
16:40	P = 8.1x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	39.4 mA, 15.14V, 2.86A
16:50	P = 8.12x10 ⁻⁷ mbar	39.2 mA, 15.07V, 2.85A

Am-nica #4: annealed @ 361°C (0.7A) for 6 hours in 5x10⁻⁸ mbar

LEED WLM) After 5th Anneal in H₂

2.4 A, 3kV screen, 0.7 kV MCP (x=0 y=-2 z=267 θ=60 ~ center)

• 100 eV 3.4V wehnelt, 120V focus, 70V grid (18μA, 0.88μA)

- center
- z+3
- z-3

• 70 eV 2.0V wehnelt, 84V focus, 491V grid (18μA, 0.69μA)

- z-3
- center
- z+3

Saturday 13.6.2020

P_{PC} = 1.6x10⁻¹⁰ mbar, P_{PC,PRE} = 4.32x10⁻² mbar, P_{LE} = >5.0x10⁻⁹ mbar => Opening GB on APC helped to remove H₂!

QMS: PC R64 @ 1.67x10⁻¹⁰ mbar

Am-nica #4 LEED - no change (one as before - spots only on one side) - no pics recorded

↳ Annealing in 1x10⁻⁷ mbar O₂ at 300°C, then at ~~500°C~~ 480°C in UHV => LEED

Venting AC, An

Sputter $W(U)$ $x=0$ $y=0$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$
 2.7×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

40 min

2.4 μ A sample

Anneal $W(U)$ w/e-Beam

Start $\Rightarrow$ 15:20	$P = 1.4 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	0.0 mA	0.0 V	0.0 A
15:21	$P = 8.6 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	38.9 mA	14.85 V	2.89 A
15:26	$P = 3.09 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	39.3 mA	15.07 V	2.87 A
15:28	$P = 1.2 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	36.4 mA	15.14 V	2.87 A
15:34	$P = 1.4 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	37.3 mA	15.4 V	2.87 A
15:39	$P = 1.3 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	37.2 mA	15.27 V	2.87 A
15:42	$P = 1.3 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	38.3 mA	15.29 V	2.87 A

LEISD $W(U)$ After Sputter Anneal + Borazine

2.4 A, 3 kV screen, 0.7 kW MEP $x=0$ $y=-2$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$

• 100 eV, 34 eV wehmet, 120 V focus, 70 V grid (18 mA, 0.88 mA)

- center	0001	$y-3$	0004
- $z+3$	0002		
- $z-3$	0003	$y+3$	0005

• 70 eV, 2.0 V wehmet, 84 V focus, 49 V grid (18 mA, 0.69 mA)

- $z-3$	0008	$y-3$	0009
- center	0006		
- $z+3$	0007	$y+3$	0010

Auger $W(U)$ After Sputter Anneal

2.42 A, 3.4 V wehmet, 1600 V focus, 0.15 kW screen, $\tau=1.5$, $\theta=60$
 sens = 0.5 V, ($x=0$ $y=-2$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$ ~center) (44 μ A, 32 mA)

- center	0001 / 0002
----------	-------------

Beam C^- (200 nm): $I_0=17.3$ mA with $R_x=+0.419$, $R_y=-0.124$

Move cleaned $W(U)$ into AL $P=7.8 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar

0091 XPS $W(3P, O1s, C1s, N1s, B1s, V3)$ 700 eV 1x1 slits $E_p=20$ eV
 $x=13$ $y=-11.15$ $z=17.5$ $\theta=30^\circ$

Sputter $W(XXX)[2]$ $x=0$ $y=0$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$
 2.7×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

20 min

2.6 μ A sample

Anneal $W(XXV)[2]$ w/e-Beam heater (1 keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$ 18:20	$P = 2.6 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	0.0 mA	0.0 V	0.0 A
18:24	$P = 4.8 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar	0.0 mA	13.39 V	2.7 A
18:38	$P = 2.3 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar	0.0 mA	13.61 V	2.7 A
18:52	$P = 1.07 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar	0.0 mA	13.61 V	2.7 A
18:58	$P = 8.1 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar	0.0 mA	13.63 V	2.7 A
19:01	$P = 1.2 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar	16.1 mA	13.7 V	2.7 A
19:12	$P = 1.3 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar	16.8 mA	13.7 V	2.7 A
19:18	$P = 2.2 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar	37.5 mA	15.14 V	2.85 A
19:23	$P = 2 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar	38.1 mA	15.24 V	2.85 A

Sputter $W(XXX)[2]$ $x=2$ $y=0$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$
 2.78×10^{-6} mbar 500, 4.6 mA, 500 V Bias

Anneal $W(XXX)[2]$ w/e-Beam heater

Start $\Rightarrow$ 20:52	$P = 7.9 \times 10^{-10}$ mbar	0.15 mA	0.0 V	0.0 A
= 20:53	$P = 1.8 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar	39.1 mA	15.12 V	2.89 A
20:59	$P = 7.8 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	40.4 mA	15.29 V	2.87 A

- 092 XPS survey @ 700 eV same spot as 091
- 093 XPS Co 2p Co 3p Cls, BIS, OLS @ 1100 eV 0.5x0.5 same spot as 092
- 094 Survey @ 1100 eV same spot as 093 0.5x0.5 slits
- [XAS 110] Co L edge UHV 0V Bias 0.5 slits, Swept, BE = 17-27 eV
- [XAS 112] O K edge UHV 0V Bias 1.0 slits, Swept, BE = 24-34 eV
- 096 XPS @ ~~1100~~ 1120 eV 0.5x0.5 slits $x=13$ $y=-11.5$ $z=15.5$ $\theta=30$

LEED W(XXX)[2] After 2 spotter Anneals
 2.4A, 3 kV screen 0.7 kV MCP ($x=0$ $y=-4$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$ center)
 • 100 eV, 3.4V wehelt, 120V focus, 70V grid, (18 μ A, 0.87 μ A)
 - center 0001
 - y-3 0004
 - y+3 0003
 - z+2 0004
 - z-2 0005
 • 70 eV, 2.0V wehelt, 84V focus, 47V grid, (19 μ A, 0.7 μ A)
 - center 0006
 - y-3 0001
 - y+3 0008
 - z+2 0009
 - z-2 0010

Auger W(XXX)[2] After 2 spotter Anneals
 2.42A, 34V wehelt, 1600V focus, 0.15 kV screen $\tau=15$ sens = 0.5 V
 $\theta=90^\circ$ (center $x=0$ $y=-4$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$)

- [XAS 114] Co L edge UHV 0V Bias 1.0 slits, swept BE = 910-920 eV (Now measured w/ KE)
- [XAS 115] O K edge UHV 0V Bias 1.0 slits, swept 500-510 eV
- 097 XPS @ 700 eV 1x1 slits same spot as 096

Sunday 14 June 2020

$\lambda_{AC} = 4.4 \times 10^{-8}$ nbar, $\lambda_{AC,PRE} = 3.8 \times 10^{-1}$ nbar, $\lambda_{LLS} = UR (> 5 \times 10^{-9}$ nbar)
 $\lambda_{PE} = 1.5 \times 10^{-10}$ nbar, $\lambda_{PE,PRE} = 4.4 \times 10^{-2}$ nbar; High Z: 2nd stage: 5×10^{-8} nbar, else UR

Co foil: anneal in UHV to 156 °C in 1×10^{-7} nbar O₂ for 30', then annealing in UHV to 250 °C

$I_0 = 17.3 \mu$ A with $R_x = +0.422$ $R_y = -0.127$ Slits 1.0!
 $x=13$, $y=-11.00$, $z=46$, $R=30^\circ$

- XPS 098 Survey 1000 eV, 1.0 slits Polarisation: unknown, Bias = 0V (Kerblley 0V) A lot of C!
- XPS 099 Survey Co foil 1000 eV, $x=13$, $y=-11$, $z=46$ $R=30^\circ$, Slits = 1.0
- XPS 100 Survey Co foil 900 eV, see ~ 099 (x,y,z,R), 1.0 slits. Checky AES ends $I_0 = 15 \mu$ A, Pol. unknown, Beam moved!

- X [XAS 116] Co L-edge, 0V bias, UHV, $z=45$; Beam moved $\Rightarrow$ nucleus
- ✓ [XAS 117] Co L-edge, Bias = 0V, UHV, $z=45$, Swept (Kinetic = 735-755 eV) $\lambda = 4.1 \times 10^{-8}$ nbar
 ✓ to some peak broadening through the region $\Rightarrow$ Change Range to 745-755 eV
- X [XAS 118] Co L-edge, Bias = 0V, UHV, $z=45$, Swept (Kinetic = 745-755 eV), $\lambda = 4.0 \times 10^{-8}$ nbar Beam lost
- ✓ [XAS 124] Co L-edge, Bias = 20V, UHV, $z=45$, Swept (Kinetic = 765-775 eV), $\lambda = 3.9 \times 10^{-8}$ nbar Beam lost

$I_0 = 17.43 \mu$ A

- [XAS 125] Co L-edge, Bias = -20V, UHV, $z=45$, Swept (Kinetic = 765-775 eV), $\lambda = 3.9 \times 10^{-8}$ nbar, C-
- [XAS 127] Co L-edge, Bias = -40V, UHV, $z=45$, Swept (Kinetic = 785-795 eV), $\lambda = 3.8 \times 10^{-8}$ nbar, C-

- [XAS 128] O K-edge, UHV, 1.0 slits, Bias: 0V, Sweep (kinetic = 500-510 eV), $\lambda = 3.8 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar
- [XAS 129] O K-edge, UHV, 1.0 slits, Bias = -20V, Sweep (kinetic, 520-530 eV), $\lambda = 3.8 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar
- [XAS 130] O K-edge, UHV, 1.0 slits, Bias = -40V, Sweep (kinetic, 540-550 eV), $\lambda = 3.8 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar

1.0 mbar

[XAS 131] O K-edge, 1 mbar H₂O, 1.0 slits, Bias = 0V C⁻ (200 mrad)

[XAS 132] O K-edge, 1 mbar H₂O, 1.0 slits, Bias = -20V

- [XAS 133] O K-edge 1.1 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -40V
- [XAS 134] Ca L-edge 0.98 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias 0V
- [XAS 135] Ca L-edge 1 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -20V
- [XAS 136] Ca L-edge 1.1 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -40V

2 mbar

- [XAS 137] O K-edge, 2 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias 0V
- [XAS 138] O K-edge, 2 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -20V
- [XAS 139] O K-edge, 2 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -40V
- [XAS 140] Ca L-edge, 2 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias 0V

Spitter - anneal TiO₂ (110) 7x7 mm; 1h spitting [2.8 e⁻⁶ mbar Ar, 4.5 mA discharge, 300V bias]
 annealing T_o ~ 400C for 1h (+) [15.4V, 2A]

- [XAS 141] Ca L-edge, 2 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -20V
- [XAS 142] Ca L-edge, 2 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -40V
- [XAS 143] O K-edge 2.1 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias 0V
- ~~[XAS 144] O K-edge 2 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -20V~~

3 mbar

- [XAS 145] O K-edge 3 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias 0V
- [XAS 146] O K-edge 3.1 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -20V ← Beamless!

LEED for TiO₂ (110) 7x7; spots visible, some a bit diffused
 ↳ attempt anneal to 450C, 30m -20 → LEED OK

~~⊙~~ I₀ → ⊙ after beamless, try moving mirrors ⊙ 514 eV
 ⇒ could find I₀ ~ 5.1 μA ⅈ R_x = 0.5177 R_y = -0.1264

Attempt [XAS 147] To test if all aligned → signal visible
 [XAS 147] Test O K-edge 3 mbar, 1.0 slits, Bias -20V after beamless

~~I₀ after XAS 147, = 1.5 μA [energy dependent]~~

XAS Acquisition settings:		E _k -range (eV)
Ca L-edge :	Bias 0V	745-755
hv start =	-20V	765-775
	-40V	785-795 eV
O K-edge	0V	500-510 eV
hv start = 514 eV	-20V	520-530 eV
	-40V	540-550 eV

E_{pass} = 100 eV, Sweep, kinetic, ADC, Index, Time 0.04, Size = 0.25, IR = 1

[XAS 142] O K-edge 3 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -40 V

I_0 @ 764 eV ; ~12.8 nA

[XAS 149] Co L-edge 3 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias 0V
 [XAS 150] Co L-edge 3 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -20V
 [XAS 151] Co L-edge 3 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -40V

4 mbar

[XAS 153] O K-edge 4 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias 0V
 [XAS 154] O K-edge 4 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -20V
 [XAS 155] O K-edge 3.9 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -40V
 [XAS 156] Co L-edge 4 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias 0V
 [XAS 157] Co L-edge 4 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -20V
 [XAS 158] Co L-edge 3.9 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -40V

5 mbar

[XAS 159] O K-edge 5 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias 0V
 [XAS 160] O K-edge 5 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -20V
 [XAS 161] O K-edge 5 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -40V
 [XAS 162] Co L-edge 5 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias 0V
 [XAS 163] Co L-edge 5 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -20V
 [XAS 164] Co L-edge 5 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias -40V

I_0 @ 1900 eV ; 18.4 nA $R_x = +0.517$, $R_y = -0.1264$

6 mbar

[XAS 166] O K-edge 6 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = 0V
 [XAS 167] O K-edge 6 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = 0V (repeat, more stable) $q = 6.05$ mbar
 [XAS 168] O K-edge 6.1 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -20V
 [XAS 169] O K-edge 6.1 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -40V
 [XAS 170] Co L-edge 6.1 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = 0V
 [XAS 171] Co L-edge 6.1 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -20V
 [XAS 172] Co L-edge 6.1 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -40V

9 mbar $R_x = +0.422$ $R_y = -0.1254$ $I_0 = 17.3$ nA

[XAS 174] O K-edge 9.0 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = 0V
 [XAS 175] O K-edge 8.9 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -20V
 [XAS 176] O K-edge 8.9 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -40V
 [XAS 177] Co L-edge 8.8 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = 0V
 [XAS 178] - Co L-edge 8.8 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -20V Optimized @ $R_y = 805$ eV, I close to zero
 [XAS 179] - Co L-edge 8.8 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -40V
 [XAS 180] - Co L-edge 8.8 mbar, 1.0 slit, Bias = -4.1V (Color = 749.1 - 759.1) Beam Loss

Sputter $W(M)$ $x=0$ $y=0$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$ 20 mbar
 2.68×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.6 mA, 500 V Bias

Anneal $W(M)$ w/e-Beam header

start $\Rightarrow$ 11:40 $P = 1.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.21 mA, 0.0 V, 0.0 A
 11:41 $P = 1.84 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar 35.9 mA, 14.78 V, 2.87 A
 11:46 $P = 2.0 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 36.3 mA, 15.24 V, 2.87 A
 11:50 $P = 2.2 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 32.6 mA, 15.21 V, 2.86 A
 11:56 $P = 2.1 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 33.2 mA, 15.29 V, 2.86 A
 12:00 $P = 2.05 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 33.8 mA, 15.29 V, 2.86 A

Co foil: $I_v = 805_eV$

Bins	Current (A)
-6V	5.4×10^{-8}
-5V	2×10^{-8}
-4V	7×10^{-9}
-3V	4.8×10^{-9} 1.0×10^{-10}
-2V	4.8×10^{-9} -5×10^{-9}
-1V	-8.2×10^{-8}
0V	-1×10^{-7}
-4.1V	$+5 \times 10^{-9}$

- [XAS 181] Co L-edge 9.1 mbars H_2O Bins = -4.1V 1.0 shifts
- [XAS 182] Co L-edge 9.2 mbars H_2O Bins = -4.0V 1.0 shifts
- [XAS 183] Co L-edge 9.3 mbars H_2O Bins = -3.9
- [XAS 186] Co L-edge 9.4 mbars H_2O Bins = -3.95
- [XAS 187] Co L-edge 9.5 mbars H_2O Bins = -4.1V

LEED $W(M)$ After Benzene exposure
 2.4A, 3 mV screen, 0.7 mV MCP (center $x=0$ $y=-3$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$)
 • 100 eV, 3.4V wehnelt, 120V focus, 70V grid (17 μA , 0.87 μA)
 center, $y-3$, $y+3$, $z+2$, $z-2$, Bkd ($z=259$)
 • 70 eV, 2.0V wehnelt 120V focus, 49V grid (18 μA , 0.69 μA)
 Bkd ($z=259$),

- [XAS 188] Co L-edge 9.4 mbars H_2O Bins = -4.1V
- [XAS 194] Co L-edge 9.5 mbars H_2O Bins = -3.9V

Keilbing reshorted

X [XAS 195] Co L-edge 9.5 mbars H_2O Bins = -4.1V there was no beam
 $I_0 = 170 \mu A$

- [XAS 196] Co L-edge 9.5 mbars H_2O Bins = -4.1V
- [XAS 197] O k-edge 9.5 mbars H_2O Bins = -4.1V
- [XAS 198] Co L-edge 23 mbars H_2O Bins = -2.3V

Avgar $W(M)$ After Benzene
 2.41A, 3.4V wehnelt, 1600V focus, 0.15 mV screen, $\tau=1s$, sens = 0.5V
 $\theta=90^\circ$ (center $x=0$ $y=-3$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$) (44 μA , 32 μA)
 - center (0001/0002) $y-3$ (0003)

[XAS 199] Co L-edge, 24 mbars H_2O , Bins = 0V

Sputter $W(XXX)[2]$ $X=2$ $Y=0$ $Z=38$ $\theta=315$
 2.9 $\times 10^{-6}$ mbar 500V, 4.5 mA, 500V Bias

[XAS 200] Co L-edge, 24 mbars H_2O , Bins = -20V

Anneal $W(XXX)[2]$ w/o Beam heater (1keV)
 start $\Rightarrow$ 14:57 $P = 2.4 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.2 mA, 0.0A, 0.0V
 Benzene $\rightarrow$ 14:58 $P = 1.6 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar 35.9 mA, 2.9A, 15.14V
 15:02 $P = 2.6 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 42.4 mA, 2.89A, 15.43V
 15:10 $P = 3 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 38.5 mA, 2.89A, 15.58V

- [XAS 201] Co L-edge, 24 mbars H_2O , Bins = -40V
- [XAS 202] Co L-edge, 24 mbars H_2O , Bins = -1.7V
- [XAS 203] O k-edge, 24 mbars H_2O , Bins = -1.7V
- [XAS 204] O k-edge, 24 mbars H_2O , Bins = 0V
- ? [XAS 205] O k-edge, 24 mbars H_2O , Bins = -20V
- X [XAS 206] O k-edge, 24 mbars H_2O , Bins = -40V probably no beam
- [XAS 207] - repeat of 206 Bins = -40V
- [XAS 208] - repeat of 205 Bins = -20V ? Are they moving the beam?

L7 Conclusion: works with 10 mbars very well. Still needs to be tested @ 20-24 mbars / find max pressure where it works
 XPS after XAS (same spot): 101 Survey 1000 eV

Auger After Borazine w/ (xxx) [2]
 2.41 A, 34V wehnelt 0.15 mm screen 1600V focus $\chi=15$, sens = 0.5V, $\theta=90$
 (x=0 y=-3 z=267 $\theta=60$ -center) 45 mA, 33 uA
 - center 0001 / 0002
 - z+3 0003 / 0004
 - z-3 0005

I_a evening: 17.4 μ A @ 1000 eV, $\chi=15$

Aligning sample: Spot "A" $\rightarrow$ x=13, y=-13, z=16.3, R=30
 Spot "B" $\rightarrow$ x=13, y=-13, z=19.3, R=30

Q102 XPS Survey 1000 eV spot "B", 5x
 Q103 XPS Ti 2p, O 1s, C 1s 1000 eV spot "A", 30x, $p=4.2 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar
 $\rightarrow$ O 1s, C 1s ranges reduced a bit after (unnecessarily wide)

No beam, exposing sample to 2 mbar H₂O for 15m [MMS; 0:12 $\rightarrow$ 0:27]

Note: 1 mbar H₂O in chamber $\Rightarrow \sim 4 \times 10^{-2}$ Torr in MMS
 returns to HV, move spot "B"

Q104 XPS Ti 2p, O 1s, C 1s 1000 eV spot "B", 45x, $p < 2.6 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar
 During 1 mbar H₂O + 1 mbar O₂ (MMS; 2:02 $\rightarrow$ 3:05)

Q105 XPS Ti 2p, O 1s, C 1s 1000 eV spot "A", 700x, $p=2$ mbar
 $\hookrightarrow$ no irradiation before start! ~ 1 h total irradiation

pump to HV with beam on

Q107 XPS Ti 2p, O 1s, C 1s 1000 eV spot "A", $\times 45$, $p < 5 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar
 Q108 XPS Ti 2p, O 1s, C 1s 1000 eV, spot "B", $\times 45$

$\hookrightarrow$ C 1s double compared to 107! cleaning beam effect

Leaking in AC ~ 2 mbar H₂O, 15m, pump to HV

Q109 XPS Ti 2p, O 1s, C 1s 1000 eV spot "B", $p < 5 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar

Leaking ~ 15 mbar H₂O + 15 mbar O₂, beam on "A" for ~ 30 m

$\hookrightarrow$ MMS: $\sim 2 \times 10^{-6}$ Torr for H₂O before O₂ [6:45]

Pump back to HV, $p < 5 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar

Q110 XPS Ti 2p, O 1s, C 1s 1000 eV spot "A", $\times 60$
 Q111 XPS Ti 2p, O 1s, C 1s 1000 eV spot "B", $\times 60$

similar result to 111 mbar H₂O + O₂

I_a end = 17.1 μ A

Sputter w/ (xxx) x=0 y=0 z=3.8 $\theta=315$
 3.1×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.6 mA, 500V bias 2.66 μ A sample

Anneal w/ (u) w/ e-beam (1 keV)

start $\Rightarrow$ 13:13 $p=5.3 \times 10^{-10}$ 0.1 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
 13:14 $p=9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 37.3 mA, 2.92 A, 15.12 V
 13:18 $p=1.3 \times 10^{-8}$ 43.6 mA, 2.89 A, 15.24 V
 13:20 $p=2.5 \times 10^{-6}$ 41.5 mA, 2.89 A, 15.51 V
 13:26 $p=3.7 \times 10^{-6}$ 37.7 mA, 2.89 A, 15.58 V
 13:28 $p=3.7 \times 10^{-6}$ 37 mA, 2.89 A, 15.6 V

UBED w/ (u) after Borazine

2.4 A, 0.7 mV wehnelt 3 kV screen (x=0 y=2 z=267 $\theta=60$ -center)
 • 100 eV, 34V wehnelt, 160V focus 70V grid (1.8 mA, 0.9 mA)
 • 70 eV, 20V wehnelt, 80V, 49V, (1.8 mA, 0.9 mA)

AC + Analyser needed: 0.5/1.0 core installed

Wednesday 17.6.2020

$I_{AC1} = 7.2 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar, $I_{PRE} = 3.7 \times 10^{-1}$ mbar, $I_{LLS} = < 5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar
 $I_{PC} = 1.88 \times 10^{-10}$ mbar, $I_{PC-PRE} = 4.3 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar

$I_0 = 18.25 \mu A$ @ 1000 eV, 10 slits $R_x = 0.528$ $R_r = -0.130$

Power outage - SLS machine down. No water cooling. Beamline in 4uv. Endstation OK. Analyser - setting further to 700 Ha

Sputter W_2O $x=0$ $y=0$ $z=-3.8$ $\theta=315$ 30 min
 3.2×10^{-6} mbar 500 V 4.6 mA 0 V Bias 1.2 mA sample

Anneal W_2O ~~to 700 Ha~~ w/c-Beam
Start => 8:28 $P = 3.3 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.1 mA 0.0A, 0.0V
8:29 $P = 2.0 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar 31.5 mA 2.88A 14.92V
8:33 $P = 8.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 35.8 mA 2.85A 15.07V

LEISD W_2O After Sputter Anneal
2.4A, 3kV screen, 0.7kV MCP, $x=20$ $y=-4$ $z=26.7$ $\theta=0^\circ$
• 100 eV 3.4 V wehelt, 120V focus, 70V grid, (20uA, 0.91uA)
- center $y-3$, $y+3$, $z+3$, $z-3$
• 70 eV 2.0 V wehelt, 84V focus, 47V grid, (20uA, 0.4uA)
• 47 eV 0.9 V wehelt, 56V focus, 32V grid, (16uA, 0.48uA)
• 28 eV 0.0 V wehelt, 33V focus, 19V grid, (15uA, 0.26uA)

$I_0 = 18.2 \mu A$ @ $R_x = +0.585$, $R_r = -0.135$

[XAS 209] Cu_2O (M) Cu L-edge $x=13$ $y=-12.95$ $z=17.5$, $R=30^\circ$ 910-920 eV KE
[XAS 210] W_2O (U) O k-edge same spot as 209 500-510 eV KE
[XAS 211] Cu_2O (U) O k-edge new spot $x=13$ $y=-12.95$ $z=16.5$ $R=30$
[XAS 212] W_2O (U) W L-edge same spot as 211

HBN on W (U)

[XAS 213] W (U) W L-edge $x=13$ $y=-11.25$ $z=17.5$ $R=30$
[XAS 214] W (U) O k-edge same spot as 213

112 XPS survey at 700 eV, same spot as XAS 213-214 x10

113 XPS BIS, CIS, NIS, OIS, W3p, VB @ 700 eV same spot 112 x30

114 XPS survey @ 1120 eV same spot x10

115 XPS $Cu 2p$, $O 1s$, $N 1s$, $B 1s$, $Cu 3p$ @ 1120 eV x30 same spot

→ spot [2] => $x=13$ $y=-11.2$ $z=15.5$ / [1] => $x=13$ $y=-11.25$ $z=17.5$

116 XPS $Cu 2p$, $C 1s$, $O 1s$, $B 1s$, $Cu 3p$, @ 1120 eV, x30 spot [2]

[XAS 215] Cu (M) Cu L-edge spot [2], 910-920 eV KE

[XAS 216] O k-edge spot [2], Cu (M), 500-510 eV KE

118 XPS $Cu 3p$, $O 1s$, $B 1s$, $N 1s$, $C 1s$, VB @ 700 eV x30 [2]

Backfill 1×10^{-3} mbar O_2 in AC
 119 XPS Cu 3p, O 1s, C 1s, N 1s, B 1s, VB @ 700 eV, 30x, 10^{-3} mbar O_2
 Beam loss during measurement! [Iter 23/24] I_0 (1000 eV) after $\approx 15.8 \mu A$
~~120 XPS; 7x continuation of "119"~~
 I_0 after: $17 \mu A$

[XAS 217] Cu L-edge 910-920 eV KE
 [XAS 218] O K-edge 500-510 eV KE

Pump back to HV ($p < 5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ mbar)
 [XAS 219] O K-edge 500-510 eV KE
 [XAS 220] Cu L-edge 910-920 eV KE

121 XPS Cu 3p, O 1s, C 1s, N 1s, B 1s, VB @ 700 eV, 30x, $p \sim 7 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar
 122 XPS Cu 2p, C 1s, O 1s, B 1s, Cu 3p @ 1120 eV, 30x, $p \sim 5 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar

LEED $W(\mu m)$ After O_2 exposure
 2.4A, 3 mV screen, 0.7 kV MCP ($x=0$ $y=-3$ $z=2e7$ $\theta=60$)
 • 100 eV, 34 V wehnelt, 120V focus, 40V grid, (20 μA , 0.89 μA)
 center $y-3$ $y+3$ $z+3$ $z-3$ Bnd ($z=259$)
 • 70 eV, 20V wehnelt, 84V, 49V grid (20 μA 0.7 μA)

WBN-Cu ESCA $x=13$ $y=-11.4$ $z=17.5$ $R=30^\circ$
 [XAS 222] Cu L-edge, $x=13$, $y=-11.4$, $z=17.5$, $R=30^\circ$, slit=1.0 KEV 910-920
 [XAS 223] O K-edge, $x=13$, $y=-11.4$, $z=17.5$, $R=30^\circ$, slit=1.0 KEV 500-510
 XPS 124 Survey at 700 eV, same spot as XAS, slit=1.0 x10
 XPS 125 Cu 3p, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s, C 1s, VB, slit=1.0 x30

Back to WBN-W(μm) original

XPS 126 W 3p O 1s B 1s N 1s C 1s VB @ 700 eV 1x1 $x=14$ $y=-11.15$ $z=17.5$ $R=30$
 XPS 127 W 3p O 1s B 1s N 1s C 1s VB @ 700 eV same spot as 126
 close GV at iteration 1 Mass spec at 09:35:00
 O_2 , 8×10^{-4} at iteration 2
 2.5×10^{-2} at iteration 3
 5×10^{-2} at iteration 4

start scanning 5-40 Mass spec end at 10:47:23

[XAS 224] W L-edge same spot as XPS 126-127, 5×10^{-2} mbar, 1x1 slits
 [XAS 225] O K-edge same spot 1x1 slits, 5×10^{-2} mbar
 close leak valve + open GV 11:22:00
 8.4×10^{-7} mbar after 2 min

XPS 129 W 3p O 1s, N 1s, C 1s, B 1s VB @ 700 eV 1x1 slits some spot
 2.8×10^{-7} mbar at start

[XAS 226] W L-edge same spot as XPS 129, 1x1 slits, UVV
 [XAS 227] O K-edge same spot as XAS 226, 1x1 slits, UVV

WBN W(μm) ESCA

[XAS 228] W L-edge New spot $x=14$ $y=-11.35$ $z=17.5$ $R=30$, 1x1 slits, UVV
 [XAS 229] O K-edge same spot as 228
 XPS 131 W 3p, O 1s, C 1s, B 1s, N 1s VB 1x1 slits some spot as XAS 228-229

LEED W(M) After 0.05 mbar O_2
 2.4A 3kV screen 0.7kV MCP ($x=0$ $y=20$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$ center)
 • 100eV 3.4V wehnelt, 120V focus 70V grid, (20nA, 0.8nA)
 $y-3$, center, $y+3$, $z+2$, $z-2$ (Bwd $z=259$)
 • 70eV 2.0V wehnelt, 84V focus, 49V grid, (19nA, 0.68nA)

Back to MBN W(M) original

[XAS 230] Cu L-edge New spot $x=12.5$ $y=-11.2$ $z=17.5$ $R=30$ 1X1 slits, UHV

[XAS 231] O K-edge, same spot, UHV

XPS 133 $A_v=7000V$: Cu 3p, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s, C 1s, VB, 10 slits, one spot in XAS

XPS 134 $h\nu=1120eV$ Cu 3p, Cu 2p O 1s, B 1s, C 1s 1X1 slits Same spot 133

New spot: $x=12.5$, $y=-11.3$, $z=17$, $R=30^\circ$

135 XPS @ 700eV, 10 slits Cu 3p, B 1s, N 1s

136 XPS @ 700 1X1 slits Cu 3p, C 1s, B 1s, N 1s, O 1s, VB Same spot as 133-134

Close GV at Iteration 1

1×10^{-3} mbar at 2

9×10^{-1} mbar at 3

Scan from 5-50 Mass spec at 01:45:00

[XAS 232] Cu L-edge same spot as XPS 136, 1X1 slits, 1 mbar O_2

[XAS 233] O K-edge same spot as XAS 232, 1X1 slits, 1 mbar O_2

[XAS 234] O K-edge Bias -10V - repeat of 233 - 510-520 eV To correct polarity

HV pump → [XAS 235] Cu L-edge Bias -10V 920-930 eV KE - repeat of 232

137 XPS @ 1100 eV 1X1 slits Cu 2p, Cu 3p, O 1s, C 1s, B 1s Same spot as XAS
 1.4×10^{-7} mbar by iteration 6

138 XPS @ 700 eV - Cu 3p, C 1s, B 1s, N 1s, O 1s, VB x30

[XAS 236] Cu L-edge Bias 0V 910-920 eV KE

[XAS 237] O K-edge Bias 0V 500-510 eV KE

139 XPS @ 720 eV B 1s [Test ~~vs~~ presence vs Auger over (to)]

$$I_0(700 eV) = 8.45 nA \quad I_0(720 eV) = 8.65 nA$$

LEED W(M) After 1 mbar O_2
 2.4A, 3kV screen, 0.7kV MCP ($x=0$ $y=20$ $z=267$ $\theta=60$)
 • 100 eV 3.4V wehnelt, 120V focus, 70V grid, (20nA, 0.88nA)
 - center, $y-2$, $y+2$, $z+2$, $z-2$, ($z=259$) Bwd
 • 70 eV, 2.0V wehnelt, 84V, 49V, 19nA, 0.7nA
 Bwd → center, $y-2$, $y+2$, centerish $y+0.5$, $z+2$, $z-2$

#5 Spot: $x=13.5$ $y=-11.2$ $z=17.5$ $R=30$

140 XPS @ 720 eV B 1s x30

141 XPS @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s, C 1s, VB x30

142 XPS @ 1120 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, C 1s, B 1s, Cu 2p x30

[XAS 238] O K-edge Bias 0V 500-510 KE

[XAS 239] Cu L-edge Bias 0V 910-920 KE

Heating to 50°C [R_{TE100} ~ 119]

! after LBED O₂ k-edge change intensity / O XPS ratio

[XAS 240] Cu L-edge Bias 0V, 910-920 KE
 [XAS 241] O K-edge Bias 0V, 500-510 KE
 143 XPS @ 720 eV B1s x30
 144 XPS @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O1s, B1s, N1s, C1s, VB x30
 ramp to 75°C; XPS start immediately, T reached at iteration #

XPS 145 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O1s, B1s, N1s, C1s, VB
Scan 8: T = 75°C 129.3 s

XPS 146: B1s 720 eV

[XAS 242] O K-edge @ 75°C

[XAS 243] Cu L-edge @ 75°C

XPS 147 Started while heating up from 75°C to 100°C: Cu 3p, O1s, B1s, N1s, C1s, VB, B1s 700 eV

100°C

XPS 148: 700 eV, 1.0 slits Cu 3p, O1s, B1s, N1s, C1s, VB $\lambda = 5.8 \times 10^{-8}$ cm

XPS 149 720 eV B1s

[XAS 244] Cu L-edge @ 100°C

[XAS 245] O K-edge @ 100°C

LBED after heating following O₂ exposure
 2.4A, 3 mV screen, 0.7 kV MCP, (X=0 y=-1 z=267 $\theta = 60^\circ$)
 • 100 eV 3.4 V wehmet, 120 V focus, 70 V grid 18 μ A, 0.8 μ A
 - center y-2, y-5, y+2, z+2, z-2 (Brd z=259)
 • 70 eV 2.0 V wehmet, 84 V focus, 49 V grid (18 μ A, 0.68 μ A)
 - Brd z=259, center, y-2, y-5, z+2, (z+2 y+3), z-2

Move CUH Back to UHV RT in AC

XPS 150 @ 700 eV 1x1 slits, W3P, O1s, C1s, N1s, B1s, VB
spot 6 X = 14.5 y = -11 z = 15.5 $\theta = 30^\circ$

XPS 151 B1s @ 720 eV same params 150

[XAS 246] O K-edge UHV, RT

[XAS 248] Cu L-edge UHV, RT

XPS 152 @ 1100 eV 1x1 slits W2P, W3P O1s, C1s some spot

100°C

XPS 153 @ 700 eV 1x1 slits W3P, O1s, C1s, N1s, B1s, VB some spot
Scan from iteration 16 - 45 for 100°C (4V, 0.42A)
lost Beam at iteration 45 for ~30 min

[XAS 249] Cu L-edge UHV, 100°C @ I_b = 16.2 μ A. Beamline optics still cold.

[XAS 250] O K-edge UHV, 100°C

Rx/Rv optimized: new I₀ = 17.3 μ A (was 12 μ A due to the optics warming up): R_x = +0.584, R_v = -0.132

XPS 154 @ 700 eV 1x1 slits W3P O1s B1s C1s N1s VB same spot
close GV at iteration 1 00:20:00 in mass spec
1x10⁻³ whar at iteration 3
scan from 3 - 32

XPS 155 @ 720 eV B1s
[XAS 251] O K-edge 0.001 whar O₂, 100°C
[XAS 252] Cu L-edge 0.001 whar O₂, 100°C 9.3×10^{-4} whar at end

XPS 156 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, C 1s, B 1s, N 1s VB Some spot 1x1 slits
 2.3×10^{-3} at iteration 2
 2×10^{-2} at 3
 5×10^{-2} at 4

Scan from 4-33

XPS 157 @ 720 eV B 1s

[XAS 253] Cu L-edge 0.05 mbar, 100°C
 [XAS 255] O K-edge 0.05 mbar, 100°C

XPS 158 @ 700 eV C 1s, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s, Cu 3p, VB 1x1 slits, some spot
 9.7×10^{-1} mbar by iteration 1
 Scan from 3-52

XPS 159 @ 720 eV B 1s 1 mbar O₂ x50

[XAS 256] Cu L-edge 910-920 eV KE 1 mbar O₂, 100°C
 [XAS 257] O K-edge 500-510 eV KE 1 mbar 100°C

↓ Pump to HV after scan start

XPS 160 @ 700 eV, Cu 3p, O 1s, C 1s, B 1s, N 1s, VB
 Iter. 2: HV reached (1E-6)
 Iter. 6: start cooling (pV 2E-7)
 Iter. 33: R ~ 114 Ω ⇒ T ~ 36°C

Start: 38 → 67

XPS 161 @ 720 eV B 1s x30

XPS 162 @ 1120 eV Cu 2p, C 1s, O 1s, B 1s, Cu 3p x30

[XAS 258] Cu L-edge 910-920 eV KE, HV RT

[XAS 259] O K-edge 500-510 eV KE, HV RT

Move to spot #7: x=14.5 y=-11.05 z=16 R=30

[XAS 260] Cu L-edge 910-920 eV KE

[XAS 261] O K-edge 500-510 eV KE

XPS 163 @ 720 eV B 1s x30

XPS 164 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s, C 1s, VB x30

LEED After O₂ exposure at temp

2.4A, 3kV, 0.7 mCP

- 100 eV
- center y-2, y+2, y-4, z+2, z-2; Blvd z=259
- 70 eV
- (z=259 Blvd), z-2, z+2, y-4, y-2, y+3, center

Spot # 8: x=14.5 y=-11.05 z=18.5 R=30

[XAS 262] O K-edge 500-510 eV KE

[XAS 263] Cu L-edge 910-920 eV KE

XPS 165 @ 720 eV B 1s x30

XPS 166 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s, C 1s, VB

L₁ 1-30: HV, RT

31: start heating to 150°C

44: 146°C

47: 2×10^{-3} at iteration 47

48: 5×10^{-1} mbar 162.82 max T

49: 1 mbar

Scan from 49-55

close O₂ notice change in sample

3×10^{-7} mbar at iteration 87
 Turn of heating at 1.9×10^{-7} , iteration 89
 1×10^{-7} mbar, 105°C at iteration 93
 6.4×10^{-8} mbar, 65°C at iteration 100
 5×10^{-8} mbar, 50°C at iteration 107
 Finish at 119 iterations $\sim 40^\circ\text{C}$

[XAS 264] O k-edge UHV, 30°C , same spot

[XAS 265] Cu L-edge UHV, 30°C , same spot

[XAS 266] Cu L-edge UHV, RT

[XAS 267] O k-edge UHV, RT

New spot
 $x = 14.5$ $y = -11.05$
 $z = 15$ $\theta = 30$

XPS 168 @ 700 O 1S, C 1S, N 1S, B 1S, Cu 3P, VB, 1x1 slits, UHV, RT

XPS 169 @ 720 B 1S

Analysis

Dip position @ $x = 1.0$, $y = 3.8$, $R = 30^\circ$

$I_0 = 18.3 \mu\text{A}$ $R_x = +0$

Analysis sample: 3502 ops @ 1000 eV, 1.0 slits

XPS 170 Survey 1000 eV, $x = 14$, $y = -9.75$, $z = 47$, $R = 30^\circ$

$p = 1.6 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar

XPS 171 Sr 3p, C 1s, same position as 170

$p = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar

XPS 172 O 1S, C 1S, @ 860 eV

$p = 6.9 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar

XPS 173 Cu 3P, C 1S, @ 7730 eV

$p = 6.7 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar

XPS 174 Survey, @ 7000 eV

$p = 6.4 \times 10^{-7}$

XPS 175 Label, C 1S, @ 570 eV

$p = 6.3 \times 10^{-7}$

XPS 176 Sr 3d, C 1S, @ 600 eV

$p = 3.5 \times 10^{-7}$

XPS 178 Cu 3P, C 1S, @ 550 eV

$p = 3.3 \times 10^{-7}$

slit strong O K edge $\rightarrow$ change HV

XPS 180 Cu 3P, C 1S, @ 600 eV

$p = 3.7 \times 10^{-7}$

XPS 187 O 1S, C 1S, @ 7070 eV

$p = 2.4 \times 10^{-7}$

XPS 182 Cu 3P, C 1S, @ 7280 eV

$p = 2.2 \times 10^{-7}$

New spot: $x = 14$, $y = -9.75$, $z = 47.3$, $R = 30^\circ$

XPS 184 Survey @ 7000 eV (sum 1) $p = 1.7 \times 10^{-7}$

New spot $x = 14$, $y = -9.75$, $z = 47.6$, $R = 30^\circ$

XPS 184 Survey @ 7000 eV (sum 2)

XPS 185 Sr 3d, Label, C 1S, @ 800 eV

$p = 1.9 \times 10^{-7}$

XPS 186 Cu 3P, C 1S, @ 850 eV

$p = 1.4 \times 10^{-7}$

XPS 187 O 1S, C 1S, @ 7370 eV

$p = 2.2 \times 10^{-7}$

Change Spot

Co L edge MEXAFS No 268

$p = 1.7 \times 10^{-7}$

$x = 6$, $y = -1.8$, $z = 5$, $R = 30^\circ$ $\leftarrow$

position where the sample was
 dip in K α for first EC measurement

New measuring position

$x = 14$, $y = 9.8$, $z = 47.6$, $R = 30^\circ$

XPS 188 Survey 7000 eV

New position $x = 14$, $y = 9.8$, $z = 48.4$, $R = 30^\circ$

XPS 189 Survey 7000 eV

Not good go back to previous position: it was better

$x = 14$, $y = 9.8$, $z = 47.6$, $R = 30^\circ$

XPS 180 Sr 3d / Cu 3P / C 1S @ 600 eV

XPS 197 CO2P, C1S $x=14, y=9.8, z=47.6$ @ 1000 eV $p=9.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$
 XPS 198 O1S/C1S @ 1070 eV
 XPS 193 Survey @ 1000 eV
 XPS 194 Sn3d, La4d, C1S @ 900 eV
 XPS 195 Sn3d @ 900 eV
 XPS 196 CO3P, C1S @ 970 eV
 XPS 197 O1S/C1S @ 1370 eV
 Co L Edge 269

Dip coordinates for EC: $x=5, y=-5, z=10, R=-10$

After EC measurement position: $x=14, y=-9.8, z=47, R=30$

XPS 198 Survey @ 1000 eV $p=1 \text{ mbar}$
~~change position~~ $x=14, y=-9.8, z=48, R=30$
 XPS 199 Survey @ 1000 eV
 XPS 200 Sn3d, CO3P, C1S @ 600 eV
 XPS 201 CO2P, C1S @ 1280 eV
 XPS 202 O1S, C1S @ 1070
 XPS 203 Sn3d, C1S @ 600 eV
 XPS 204 Survey @ 1000 eV
 XPS 205 Sn3d, La4d, C1S @ 900 eV
 XPS 206 Sn3d @ 920 eV
 XPS 207 CO3P, C1S @ 970 eV
 XPS 208 O1S, C1S @ 1370 eV $p=9.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$

NEXAFS 270 Co L Edge

HV: 4×10^{-9} Ahu, $x=14, y=-9.85, z=49, R=30$

XPS 209 Survey 1000 eV - a lot of carbon, $E_p=209$ eV

New spot: $x=14, y=-9.9, z=49.5, R=30$

XPS 210 Survey 1000 eV $E_p=209$ eV

XPS 212 Survey 1000 eV at $x=14, y=-9.9, z=44, R=30$

XPS 213 Sn3d, C1S, CO3P 600 eV

XPS 214 CO2P, C1S 1280 eV

XPS 215 O1S, C1S 1070 eV

XPS 216 Survey 1000 eV

XAS 271: Co L-edge (Fixed, $E_{\text{calor}}=710$ eV, $T_{\text{inc}}=0.08$), new spot vs XPS

XAS 274 Co L-edge, new spot ($z=43.5$), Fixed, $E_{\text{calor}}=745$ eV

XAS 275 Co L-edge, repeat of 271 ($z=44$) with Fixed, $E_{\text{calor}}=745$ eV

XPS 222 Sn3d, C1S ($z=43.5$) 920 eV

XPS 223 CO3P, C1S 970 eV

XPS 224 O1S, C1S 1370 eV

~~XPS 225 Survey 1000 eV~~
~~XPS 226 Sn3d, C1S 600 eV~~
~~XPS 227 CO2P, C1S 1280 eV~~
~~XPS 228 O1S, C1S 1070 eV~~
~~XPS 229 Survey 1000 eV~~

Dino's N:O

Inserted, $\lambda = 3.3 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar

$x=14, y=-10.35, z=45.5, R=35^\circ$

XPS 225 Survey @ 1000 eV, 1.0 slits

XPS 226 Survey @ 1000 eV

A few stopped XPS scans...

XPS 230 N: $2p, Cl 1s$ @ 1150 eV Beam issues - decaying beam slits 1.0

XPS 231 N: $2p, Cl 1s$ @ 1150 eV, 0.3 slits

Top up needed.

XPS 233 $h\nu = 1150$, slits = 0.3, $I_0 = 0.62 \mu A$, $x=14, y=-10.4, z=44.5, R=30$ $E_p = 50$ eV
N: $2p$ (x12), O $1s$ (x2), C $1s$ (x1), VB (x1) x20 $\lambda_i = 1.5 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar, $\lambda_{end} =$
(Note, INEP is $7.29 \text{ \AA}$ for N: $2p$, $12.25 \text{ \AA}$ for O $1s$)

Annealing N:O #3 at $\sim 140^\circ C$ for ~ 45 min at $\sim 2 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mbar O_2

spot 2: $x=14, y=-10.4, z=44, R=30$

XPS 234 Survey 1000 eV pure SO x5, slit 1.0, $I_0 = 17.7 \mu A$ @ 1000 eV

$I_0 = 0.57 \mu A$ @ 1150 eV slit 0.3

still high Carbon level $\sim 30\%$ at $\sim 200^\circ C$, $\sim 5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mbar O_2

Move to ~~spot #2~~ spot #2 $x=14, y=-10.4, z=44.5, R=30$

XPS 235 Survey 1000 eV pure SO x5, slit 1.0, $p \sim 8 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Carbon not really reduced further; move on

XPS 236 $h\nu = 1150$, slits 0.3, x15
N: $2p$ (x12), O $1s$ (x2), C $1s$ (x1), VB (x3)

Time 0.08, 11er 5, step 0.25
Pass energy 100

[XAS 278] N: L-edge, ~~845-880 KE~~, Fixed mode centered 845 KE

XPS 240 @ 820 eV, VB, C $1s$, O $1s$ x20 (slits 1.0)

I_0 @ 820 = $13.4 \mu A$ (slits 1.0)

[XAS 280] O K-edge, Swept mode 500-510 KE, pure SO, Time 0.12, 11er 2

I_0 @ 1300 = 0.3 slit 0.3

Plant detector, insert KAH; EC: 0 eV, CA 1V or more

remove all, measure in 1 mbar H_2O ; spot as before $z=45.5$

XPS 241 Survey @ 1000 eV, slits 1, x2

XPS 242 @ 1150 eV slits 0.3 x20

L: N: ($2p$) (x12), O $1s$ (x2), C $1s$ (x1)

[probably x15 would have been enough]

XPS 243 820 eV, O $1s$, C $1s$, one spot x20

XPS 244 820 eV, 1.0 slits VB

[XAS 281] N: L-edge: 1.0 slits, pure SO, Fixed, 845 eV, Time 0.08, 5x (11er), $E_f = 100$ eV

[XAS 282] O K-edge: 1.0 slits, one spot, Swept 500-510, Time 0.12, 2x, $E_f = 50$ eV

New spot: $x=14, y=-10.4, z=46, R=30^\circ$
 XPS 245 VB(x2), C1s, O1s $h\nu=820\text{eV}$, 1.0 slit $\times 20$
 [XAS283] O K-edge
 [XAS284] Ni L-edge
 [XAS285] O K-edge gas phase (sample @ $V=0$)

AFTER EC CV cycling

New measurement spot: $x=14, y=-10.3, z=46, R=30, p=1\text{mbar}$

XPS 246 Survey @ 1000 eV $p=1.3\text{mbar}$
 XPS 247 Ni 2p, O1s, C1s @ 1150 eV, slit=0.3 $p=0.9\text{mbar}$
 New Spot: $x=14, y=-10.3, z=46.5, R=30, p=1\text{mbar}$
 XPS 248 Survey @ 1000 eV
 XPS 250 VB, C1s, O1s @ 820 eV $p=1\text{mbar}$

NEXAFS 287 O K Edge
 NEXAFS 288 Ni L Edge
 — go back in vacuum

New spot: $x=14, y=-10.3, z=47, R=30$
 XPS 252 Survey @ 1000 eV $p=1.4 \cdot 10^6\text{mbar}$
 XPS 253 Ni 2p, O1s, C1s @ 1150 eV slit 0.3 $\times 15, p=1.2 \cdot 10^6$
 XPS 254 O1s, C1s, VB @ 820 eV $\times 20, \text{slit } 1.0$
 NEXAFS 289 O K Edge $p=3.4 \cdot 10^7$
 NEXAFS 290 Ni L Edge $p=3.2 \cdot 10^7$

Change sample: FeNiO₂
 position approx: $x=14, y=-10.4, z=48, R=30$

NEXAFS 297 Fe L Edge (Dino) KE=588, fixed mode, time=0.08, $t_{\text{iteration}}=10$
 ↑ Test! To redo (final parameters ok)

Amol FeNiO sample $T_s \sim 250^\circ\text{C}$, $5 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{mbar } \text{O}_2$ for $\sim 25\text{min}$

XPS 255 Survey @ 1000 eV $\times 20$ (slit=1.0)
 XPS 256 @ 820 eV O1s, C1s, VB $\times 20$ [Iron only in NEXAFS]
 (15 of carbon register at scanning)
 [XAS 292] Fe L-edge
 [XAS 293] O K-edge
 XPS 257 @ 1150 eV Ni 2p (x8), O1s (x2), C1s (x1) - slit=0.3, $\times 15$

EC: CV $\times 225$; vent and pur

XPS 258 @ 1000 eV; Survey $\times 1$
 XPS 259 @ 820 eV O1s, C1s, VB $\times 20$ (slit=1.0)
 [XAS 294] O K-edge
 [XAS 295] Fe L-edge
 XPS 260 @ 1150 eV - slit=0.3, Ni 2p (8x), O1s (2x), C1s (1x) $\times 9$
 from 10; orbit feedback off, no top-up

23.6.2020

12° Venting AC, running 0.5-1.0 cone, installing 0.3-0.6 cone

$\Gamma_{ACI} = 4.8 \times 10^{-7}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{PRE} = 4.1 \times 10^{-1}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{LLS} = 1.7 \times 10^{-7}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{RC} = 1.4 \times 10^{-10}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{RC,PRE} = 4.58 \times 10^{-2}$ mbars

Him: outgassing QMS, MCP (1630V), Screen (3600V)

$I_0 = 17.2 \mu A$

Co foil, no treatment

XPS 261 Survey 1000 eV, $\Gamma = 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$ mbars, $x = 14.0$, $y = -10.8$, $z = 47$, $R = 30^\circ$

XPS 262 Survey 1000 eV -11- $z = 47.5$

[XAS 299] O K-edge HV (3.6×10^{-7} mbars), $x = 14$, $y = -10.8$, $z = 47.5$, $R = 30^\circ$, Bias = 0V

[XAS 300] Co L-edge HV (3.3×10^{-7} mbars), see position Bias = 0V

[XAS 301] Co L-edge, $\Gamma = 10$ mbars $\rightarrow$ 12 mbars Bias = -4.0V

[XAS 302] Co L-edge, $\Gamma = 12$ mbars $\rightarrow$ 13 mbars Bias = -4.1V

$I_0 = 16.5 \mu A$

[XAS 303] Co L-edge, $\Gamma = 13$ mbars (stable?) Bias = -4.1V

[XAS 304] Co L-edge, $\Gamma = 13$ mbars Bias = -4.1V

$I_0 = 16.5 \mu A$

[XAS 305] Co L-edge, $\Gamma = 13$ mbars (stable) Bias = -4.0V

[XAS 306] Co L-edge, $\Gamma = 13$ mbars (stable) - machine down. Bias = -20V

— End of Co foil for now —

$\Gamma_{ACI} = 1.4 \times 10^{-6}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{LLS} = 1.4 \times 10^{-7}$ mbars

Preparing TiO₂ (Ti) 7x7: sputter $20 \mu m$, Anneal $425^\circ C \sim 30m$

LLPBI: OK (uh?)

$\uparrow$ 300V bias, 4.5mA duty, $p = 2.6 \times 10^{-6}$ mbars Ar

QMG: p1200 over to $425^\circ C$

Note: pBN holder vent $p \sim 10^{-8}$ mbar, possible because decomposition. Might have extra C on TiO₂

24.6.2020 (Wednesday)

$\Gamma_{ACI} = 9.1 \times 10^{-8}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{PRE} = 3.8 \times 10^{-1}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{LLS} = 6.5 \times 10^{-8}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{RC} = 1.5 \times 10^{-10}$ mbars, $\Gamma_{RC,PRE} = 4.55 \times 10^{-2}$ mbars

$I_0 = 17.2 \mu A$ @ 1000 eV, 10 slits

Co foil: XPS 263: Survey @ 1000 eV, 10 slits, $x = 14$, $y = -10.95$, $z = 48.5$, $R = 30^\circ \rightarrow$ OK (in UHV)

[XAS 307] Co L-edge, standard E range with variable energy step } UHV

[XAS 308] Co L-edge, the entire E range with 0.25 eV step } UHV

[XAS 309] Co L-edge, old, variable E step, 8.2 mbars, -4.1V bias
 $\hookrightarrow$ pressure not stable $\rightarrow$ slightly going down to 8.0 at end

[XAS 310] Co L-edge, see opt, Bias -4.0V 8.0 mbars

[XAS 311] Co L-edge, same opt, Bias -3.9V 7.9 mbars $\rightarrow$ 7.8 mbars

[XAS 312] Co L-edge, same opt, $\Gamma = 11$ mbars, $\Gamma_{end} = 16$ mbars, Bias = -4.1V
 $\hookrightarrow$ bias value closed a bit at 778 eV. Aborted

[XAS 313] Co L-edge, see opt, Bias = -4.1V, $\Gamma_i = 16$ mbars, $\Gamma_{end} = 19$ mbars aborted

[XAS 314] Co L-edge, see opt, Bias = -4.1V, $\Gamma_i = 18$ mbars

[XAS 315] Co L-edge, see opt, Bias = -20V, $\Gamma_i = 19$ mbars, $\Gamma_{end} = 19$ mbars

[XAS 316] Co L-edge, same opt, Bias = -40V, $\Gamma_i = 19$ mbars, $\Gamma_{end} = 19$ mbars

[XAS 317] O K-edge, Bias = 0V, $\Gamma_i = 19$ mbars

[XAS 318] O K-edge, Bias = -20V, $\Gamma_i = 19$ mbars

[XAS 399] repeat of 318, $\Gamma_i = 19$ mbars

// Kittingly set for 2 mA range -11-

XPS 284 Survey on Co foil after H₂O exposure, E_p=50eV
 XPS 268 Survey on Co foil, E_p=20eV $\rho = 7.7 \times 10^{-7}$ mbar 1x
 Co-foil experiment finished, Pollux started at 14⁰⁰

25-06-2020

Sputter W(m) x=0 y=0 z=3.8 $\theta = 315$ 20 min
 3.2×10^{-6} mbar 490V, 4.6 mA, 500V Bias

Anneal W(m) w/e-Beam heater

Start $\Rightarrow$ 13:26	P = 2.9×10^{-9} mbar	0.17 mA, 0.0A, 0.0V
13:27	P = 1.3×10^{-8} mbar	40.5 mA, 2.89A, 15.07V
13:35	P = 9.0×10^{-9} mbar	40.9 mA, 2.87A, 15.29V
13:37	P = 9.6×10^{-9} mbar	41.2 mA, 2.86A, 15.36V

Sputter W(m) x=0 y=0 z=3.8 $\theta = 315$ 20 min
 3.05×10^{-6} mbar 500V, 4.5 mA, 500V Bias

Anneal W(m) w/e-Beam heater

Start $\Rightarrow$ 15:17	P = 3.0×10^{-9} mbar	0.29 mA, 0.0A, 0.0V
15:18	P = 6.2×10^{-9} mbar	40.33 mA, 2.88A, 15.23V
15:22	P = 6.8×10^{-9} mbar	42.6 mA, 2.87A, 15.3V

LEED after 2 sputter - Anneals

2.4A, 3ml screen, 0.7 μ W MCP, 100-70 eV
 center, z+2, z-2 (19 μ A, 0.7-0.9 μ A beam)

Sputter ~~2.79~~ W(m) x=0 y=0 z=3.8 $\theta = 315$
 2.79×10^{-6} mbar 500eV, 4.6 mA, 500eV Bias

Anneal W(m) w/e-Beam heater

Start $\Rightarrow$ 17:08	P = 6.3×10^{-9} mbar	0.17 mA, 0.0V, 0.0A
17:09	P = 4.0×10^{-9} mbar	40.3 mA, 15.07V, 2.88A
17:16	P = 6.7×10^{-9} mbar	41.8 mA, 15.36V, 2.86A
17:18	P = 7.2×10^{-9} mbar	40.6 mA, 15.29V, 2.85A

Anneal W(m) in H₂ w/e-Beam

Start $\Rightarrow$ 17:50	P = 1.8×10^{-9} mbar	0.18 mA, 0.0A, 0.0V
17:54	P = 8.03×10^{-7} mbar	0.18 mA, 0.0A, 0.0V
17:55	P = 8.2×10^{-7} mbar	41.8 mA, 2.88A, 15.2V
18:00	P = 8.2×10^{-7} mbar	40.8 mA, 2.85A, 15.29V
18:06	P = 8.2×10^{-7} mbar	41.6 mA, 2.87A, 15.36V
18:12	P = 8.2×10^{-7} mbar	40.5 mA, 2.84A, 15.36V
18:15	P = 8.2×10^{-7} mbar	40.8 mA, 2.84A, 15.36V

Anneal W(m) in H₂ w/e-Beam

Start $\Rightarrow$ 18:54	P = 8.3×10^{-10} mbar	0.18 mA, 0.0A, 0.0V
18:56	P = 7.3×10^{-7} mbar	0.18 mA, 0.0A, 0.0V
18:57	P = 7.5×10^{-7} mbar	41.2 mA, 2.87A, 15.14V
19:03	P = 7.6×10^{-7} mbar	41.8 mA, 2.85A, 15.36V
19:09	P = 7.6×10^{-7} mbar	41.1 mA, 2.84A, 15.30V
19:14	P = 7.6×10^{-7} mbar	42 mA, 2.84A, 15.36V
19:17	P = 7.6×10^{-7} mbar	42.5 mA, 2.84A, 15.4V

26 06 2020

Sputter $W(\mu)$ $x=0$ $y=0$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$
 3.03×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

1 hour

Anneal $W(\mu)$ w/e-Beam (1keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$	14:01	$P = 2.8 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	0.07 mA	0.0 V	0.0 A
	14:02	$P = 7 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	41.7 mA	15.07 V	2.87 A
	14:04	$P = 4.8 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	39.7 mA	15.14 V	2.84 A
	14:07	$P = 4.9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	40.5 mA	15.27 V	2.84 A

Sputter $W(\mu)$ $x=0$ $y=0$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$

3.0×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.6 mA, 500 V Bias

1 hour

Anneal $W(\mu)$ w/e-Beam (1keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$	15:09	$P = 2.49 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	0.08 mA	0.0 A	0.0 V
	16:04	$P = 4.7 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	42.16 mA	2.85 A	15.36 V
	16:09	$P = 2.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	41.6 mA	2.86 A	15.51 V
	16:16	$P = 2.43 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	43.2 mA	2.87 A	15.65 V

1 μ m Borazine
-1 keV

LEED after Sputter/Anneal, 2 Hz anneals, + Sputter anneal
2.4 A, 3 mV screen, 0.7 keV MCP 100 + 70 eV
center, $z+2$, $z-2$ (20 nA, 0.7-0.9 mA)

LEED After Sputter Anneal + Borazine

2.4 A, 3 mV screen, 0.7 keV MCP 100 + 70 eV
center, $z+2$, $z-2$ (20 nA, 0.7-0.9 mA)

Auger after Sputter Anneal

27 06 2020

Sputter $W(\mu)$ $x=0$ $y=-2$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$
 2×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.5 mA, 500 V Bias

40 min

Anneal $W(\mu)$ w/e-Beam Heater (1keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$	19:48	2.87×10^{-9} mbar	0.1 mA	0.0 A	0.0 V
	19:49	$P = 7.4 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	41.9 mA	2.89 A	15.29 V
	19:54	$P = 7.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	42.3 mA	2.85 A	15.36 V
	19:55	$P = 1.7 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	42.5 mA	2.86 A	15.51 V
	20:01	$P = 1.8 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	43.6 mA	2.86 A	15.58 V
	20:05	$P = 1.78 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	44.85 mA	2.86 A	15.65 V

LEED After Sputter/Anneal + 1 μ l Borazine

2.4 A, 3 mV screen, 0.7 keV MCP 100 + 70 eV
center $y-2$, $y+2$, $z+2$, $z-2$, Bkd (20 nA, 0.7-0.9 mA)

Auger After Sputter Anneal + 1 μ l Borazine

Sputter $W(\mu)$ $x=0$ $y=-2$ $z=3.8$ $\theta=315$
 3×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 4.6 mA, 500 V Bias

Anneal $W(\mu)$ w/e-Beam (1keV)

Start $\Rightarrow$	22:21	$P = 2.9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	0.17 mA	0.0 A	0.0 V
	22:22	$P = 7.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	41.2 mA	2.89 A	15.28 V
	22:27	$P = 8.0 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar	43.3 mA	2.85 A	15.37 V
	22:29	$P = 3 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	42.5 mA	2.84 A	15.58 V
	22:34	$P = 3 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar	42.9 mA	2.87 A	15.73 V

LEED After Sputter/Anneal + 1 μ l Borazine

2.4 A, 3 mV screen 0.7 keV MCP 100 + 70 eV (20 nA, 0.7-0.9 mA)

Auger after Sputter Anneal + 1 μ l Borazine

28 Oct 2020

Sputter ω (m) X20 $q = -2$ $z = 38$ $\theta = 315$
 3×10^{-6} mbar 500V, 4.5 mA, 5.10 k Bias

Anneal ω (m) w/ eBeam (1 keV)
Start $\Rightarrow$ 12:42 $P = 2.9 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 0.05 mA, 0.0A, 0.0V
12:43 $P = 8 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 41.6 mA, 2.89A, 15.3V
12:48 $P = 9.5 \times 10^{-9}$ mbar 42.6 mA, 2.84A, 15.36V
12:49 $P = 2.3 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 36.2 mA, 2.82A, 15.2V
12:53 $P = 2.4 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 38 mA, 2.84A, 15.43V
12:59 $P = 2.4 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar 38.6 mA, 2.84A, 15.5V

LEED after Sputter Anneal + 1.5 kL Benzene
2.4A, 3 mV screen, 0.7 kV MCP (20 mA, 0.7 - 0.9 mA)

Auger after Sputter Anneal + 1.5 kL Benzene
2 keV 34 V wehnelt (44 mA, 32 mA)

Oxidize ω (m) in Ar

- * Load sample in Ar $X = 14$ $q = -10.85$ $z = 15.1$ $R = 300$
- * Collect picture at spot
- * Leak 1 mbar O_2 (17:10 - 17:20 ramp pressure)
- * 1×10^{-1} mbar at 17:20
- * 1 mbar at 17:25
- * Start heating at 17:30
- * 100°C + 1 mbar 18:00 (0.6A, 5.72V)
- * 148°C + 1 mbar 18:40 (0.72A, 6.36V)
- * 150°C + 1 mbar 18:47 " " start cooling
- * 45°C + 1 mbar 19:10

LEED After Oxidation

2.4A, 3 kV screen 0.7 kV MCP 20 mA, (0.7 - 0.9 mA)

Auger After Oxidation

2 keV, 34 V wehnelt, (45 mA, 32 mA)

Anneal to 150°C in UHV

Start $\Rightarrow$ 8:50

$\Rightarrow$ 140°C (0.6A, 6.75V) 9:20

$\Rightarrow$ 150°C " " 9:30 start cooling

LEED After Oxidation

2.4A 3 kV screen 0.7 kV MCP (20 mA, 0.7 - 0.9 mA)

Auger After Oxidation

2 keV, 34 V wehnelt, (45 mA, 32 mA)

29.6.2020

$f_{Ac1} = 2.5 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar, $f_{PE1} = 3.6 \times 10^{-1}$ mbar, $f_{LLS} = 1.3 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar, $f_{PC} = 2 \times 10^{-10}$ mbar, $f_{PC,PE} = 4.48 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar

Analyzer outgassed (MCP 1630V, Screen 3600V)

$I_0 = 16.4$ mA @ 10000V, 1.0 eV, $R_x = +0.564$, $R_r = -0.136$

GA ESCA Opt 271 Cu_{3P} , O_{1s} , B_{1s} , N_{1s} , Cl_{1s} , VB @ 7000V, 1.0 eV, $x=14$, $y=-11.4$, $z=16.5$, $R=30^\circ$, HV (2.5×10^{-9} mbar)

XPS 272 B_{1s} @ 720 eV 1x1 slits same spot

XAS 320 W L-edge same spot

XAS 321 O K-edge same spot

I_0 was only 3.6 mA. New $R_x R_r$: $R_x = +0.605$, $R_r = -0.136$, $I_0 = 18.3$ mA

XPS 273 W2P, W3P, O_{1s} , B_{1s} , Cl_{1s} @ 1120 eV 1x1 slits same spot 22 scans

XPS 274 W3P, O_{1s} , Cl_{1s} , N_{1s} , B_{1s} , VB @ 700 eV 1x1 slits same spot

close GV at Iteration 1
 4.5×10^{-2} mbar 2
 4.7×10^{-1} mbar 3
1 mbar at 5

~~start heating at 6~~ (0.724A, -6.36V)
1 mbar 100°C at 10 1 mbar O_2 146°C at 31
1 mbar 136°C at 19

scan 150 +/- 10° 1 mbar from 21 - 20

~~stop cooling at 71~~
close LV at 79 (60°C)
 1.8×10^{-7} mbar 50°C 83

scan ~~from~~ ~ LVHV, R_x from 84 = 113

XPS 275 B_{1s} @ 720 eV, see position as 274

XAS 322 O K-edge, same spot, $p = 4.1 \times 10^{-8}$ mbar

XAS 323 W L-edge same spot

XPS 276 B_{1s} @ 720 eV $x=14$, $y=-11.4$, $z=17.5$, $R=30$

XPS 277 B_{1s} @ 720 eV $x=14$, $y=-11.4$, $z=19.3$, $R=30$

Switch to WBN on W(U) after Oxidation + UHV Anneal

XPS 278 B_{1s} @ 720 eV $x=14$, $y=-11.05$, $z=17$, $R=30$

XAS 324 W L-edge same spot (910-920)

XAS 325 O K-edge same spot (500-510)

XPS 280 W3P W2P O_{1s} , B_{1s} , N_{1s} , VB @ 700 eV 1x1 slits same spot

XPS 281 W3P W2P Cl_{1s} , O_{1s} , B_{1s} @ 1120 eV 1x1 slits same spot

XPS 282 W3P W2P Cl_{1s} , O_{1s} , B_{1s} @ 1120 eV 1x1 slits ~~same spot~~ $x=13$, $y=-11.15$, $z=17$, $R=30$

* Anneal W(U) ESCA w/WBN after Oxidation
start => 18:15 0.65A, 7.1V
18:45 150°C start + cooling

XPS 283 B_{1s} @ 720 eV 1x1 slits same spot x30

XPS 284 Cu_{3P} , O_{1s} , N_{1s} , Cl_{1s} , VB @ 700 eV same spot x30

XAS 326 O K-edge (500-510 KE)

XAS 327 W L-edge

XPS 285 C 1s, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s Cu 3p VB @ 700 eV same spot as 284

Close GV at iteration 1
 1×10^{-3} mbar

Scan from 4 - 33 0.001 mbar H₂O z=17

ramp up pressure to $5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mbar H₂O
[1h 20m] 37 - 81 0.05 mbar H₂O, z=16.5 x45

Sputter W(M) x=0 y=-2 z=38 R=315 50 min
 2.8×10^{-6} mbar 500 V, 9.6 mA, 500V Bias

Anneal

Start	22:00	P = 2×10^{-9} mbar	0.2 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
	22:01	P = 4×10^{-8} mbar	41.6 mA, 2.87 A, 15.29 V
	22:05	P = 1.1×10^{-8} mbar	40.6 mA, 2.83 A, 15.2 V
Baryte	22:08	P = 9.3×10^{-9} mbar	40.4 mA, 2.82 A, 15.29 V
	22:10	P = 2.8×10^{-6} mbar	35.1 mA, 2.82 A, 15.29 V
	22:15	P = 2.8×10^{-6} mbar	33.8 mA, 2.82 A, 15.32 V

ramp pressure to 1 mbar H₂O
[1h 20m] 88 - 147 1 mbar H₂O z=16

Sputter W(M) x=0 y=-2 z=38 R=315 25 min
 2.9×10^{-6} mbar 500V, 4.6 mA, 500V Bias

Anneal

Start	23:27	P = 4.1×10^{-9} mbar	0.09 mA, 0.0 A, 0.0 V
	23:28	P = 1.3×10^{-8} mbar	41.7 mA, 2.87 A, 15.36 V
	23:33	P = 1.0×10^{-8} mbar	41.7 mA, 2.83 A, 15.36 V
	23:35	P = 1.95×10^{-6} mbar	37.2 mA, 2.82 A, 15.29 V
	23:42	P = 2.08×10^{-6} mbar	35.1 mA, 2.81 A, 15.29 V

heating to $\sim 80^\circ\text{C}$: 131 Ω for Pt100, then max to 15.5 z
[1h 50m] 161 - 220 1 mbar H₂O, 80°C

Heater power $\sim 4.3\text{V}$, 0.42 A

Cool down to RT, then vacuum $\rightarrow$ open GV at IT 232
p < $5 \text{ E-}6$ mbar

[1h] 234 - 263 HV RT (same spot as 1 mbar 80°C)

XPS 286 B 1s @ 720 eV x30 same spot

XAS 328 Cu L-edge 910-920

XAS 329 O K edge 500-510

Move back to z=17

XPS 287 B 1s @ 720 eV x30

XPS 288 Cu 3p, C 1s, B 1s, N 1s, VB, air x30 @ 700 eV

XAS 330 O K-edge 500-510

XAS 331 Cu L-edge 910-920

XPS 289 @ 1120 eV Cu 3p, Cu 2p, C 1s, O 1s, B 1s x30 same spot z=17

Machine development shift start of Nov. 4

XPS 290 @ 1120 eV, z=15.5 Cu 3p, Cu 2p, C 1s, O 1s, B 1s x30, z=15.5

Cu₂O (11p) M43: e-beam anneal: IEM=35 mA @ 18V for 5'

LEED 100eV, W=3.4V

70eV, W=2.0V

47eV, W=0.9V

Cu₂O(111)

XPS 291 Survey 1100eV, 1.0 slits, Decaying beam, I_{o,i} = 333 mA, I_{o,e} = 320.1 mA, x5

x = 12, y = -15, z = 17.5, R = 30° μ = 5.3 x 10⁻⁸ mbar

XPS 292 Cu 2p, Cu 3p, O 1s @ 1100eV, same spot (1), μ = 5.2 x 10⁻⁸ mbar, I_{o,i} = 319.7 mA, x30 I_{o,e} = 301.2

Sputter W (11) x = 0 y = 0 z = 3.8 θ = 315 20 min
 2.8 x 10⁻⁶ mbar, 500V, 4.6 mA, 500V Bias

Anneal W (11) w/e Beam 1 half

Start → 12:20	P = 3.8 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	1.67 mA	0.0 A, 0.0 V
12:21	P = 1.2 x 10 ⁻⁸ mbar	42.8 mA	2.84 A, 15.2 V
12:25	P = 9.3 x 10 ⁻⁹ mbar	39.9 mA	2.81 A, 15.14 V
12:26	P = 2 x 10 ⁻⁶ mbar	37.0 mA	2.81 A, 15.24 V
12:33	P = 2.5 x 10 ⁻⁶ mbar	36.5 mA	2.82 A, 15.36 V

XPS 293 Cu 3p, O 1s, Cl 2s, VB @ 700eV, 1.0 slits, I_{o,i} = 300.5 mA, I_{o,e} = 284.5 mA

Spot 2: x = 12, y = -13, z = 16.5, R = 30°

XPS 294 700eV

Scan 1-2	HV (4.6 x 10 ⁻⁸ mbar)	I _o = 282.6
3	1 x 10 ⁻³ mbar H ₂ O	281.6
4	1 x 10 ⁻² mbar H ₂ O	281.3
5	1 x 10 ⁻¹ mbar	280.5
11	1 mbar H ₂ O	277.5
13	1.2 mbar H ₂ O	276.3
15	1.4 mbar H ₂ O	275.3
18	1.5 mbar	274.2
21	1.6 mbar	272.5
23	1.7 mbar	271.3
29	1.7 mbar	θ

Beam re-started

XPS 295 700eV, 1.0 slits, same as 294, Beam not stable I_{o,i} = 14.9 mA, I_{o,e} = 1.8 mbar H₂O

I_o optimization: 12.6 mA → 16.0 mA

XPS 296 700eV, same as XPS 295

I_o optimization: 16.2 → 16.5 mA

XPS 297 700eV, same as XPS 295 x20

XPS 298 1100eV Cu 2p, Cu 3p, O 1s x15

XPS 299 1100eV Cu 2p, O 1s x5

[XAS 332] Cu L-edge, Spot 2, 1.8 mbar H₂O, Bias = 0V

HV, Spot 2

[XAS 334] Cu L-edge, Spot 2, HV, Bias = 0V, μ = 2.5 x 10⁻⁶ mbar

XPS 300 700eV Cu 3p, O 1s, Cl 2s, VB x20, 1.0 x 10⁻⁶ mbar, Spot 2

XPS 301 1100eV Cu 2p, O 1s x30, 5 x 10⁻⁷ mbar, Spot 2; Ignore last mention - sample moved!

LEED of W (11) w/ WBN/WOx after Water Exposure
 Auger of some sample

LEED of W (11) ESCA after 3rd Sputter/Anneal + 1kL Benzene
 Auger of some sample

Anneal W (11) w/ WBN/WOx after H₂O to 150°C in UHV
 Start → 17:23 280°C set 0.65 A, 8.05 V
 17:52 151°C 0.65 A, 7.08 V spot cooling

LEED of W (11) after Anneal
 Auger of some sample

Cu₂O (11) Move leads to spot 1: X = 12, Y = -13.1, Z = 17.5

XPS 302 1100 eV Cu 2p, O 1s, x30

XPS 303 700 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, Cl 2s, VB

[XAS 335] Cu L-edge $\lambda = 2.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar

hBN - Cu w/o after H₂O + UHV anneal

XPS 304 BIS @ 720 eV 1x1 slits X = 13.5 Y = -10.95 Z = 19.1 R = 30

XPS 305 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, Cl 2s, VB, N 1s (x30)

XAS 336 Cu L-edge same spot

XAS 337 O K-edge same spot

hBN - Cu (Esca)

XPS 306 @ 720 eV B 1s x30

[X = 14 Y = -11.2 Z = 19 R = 30] SES 1

XPS 307 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, Cl 2s, N 1s, VB x30

XAS 338 O K-edge

XAS 339 Cu L-edge

move to spot 2 [Z = 17]

XAS 340 Cu L-edge

XAS 341 O K-edge

XPS 308 @ 720 eV B 1s x30

XPS 309 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, O 1s, Cl 2s, N 1s, VB x30

LEED on Cu₂O (111): 100, 70, 47 eV, no pattern visible

Dosing 1E-3 mbar H₂O; start log scan

XPS 310 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, Cl 2s, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s, VB *

→ 1-30 : 1.10⁻³ mbar H₂O Z = 17.5 (x30)

→ 34-78 5.10⁻² mbar H₂O Z = 18 (x45)

→ ramp to 1 mbar

→ 83-142 1 mbar H₂O Z = 18.5 (x60)

heat to 80°C (130 Ω)

→ 148-207 1 mbar H₂O at 80°C Z = 19 (x60)

Turn off heating; ~~stop XPS when heat to 80°C~~

~~pump to 1E-3 mbar when heat to 80°C~~

XPS 311 @ 700 eV ~~Cl 2s, O 1s, B 1s, N 1s~~ 1 mbar (x60) Z = 18 (check oxide)

XPS 312 @ 700 eV Cl 2s HV (x30) Z = 18

↳ likely not effect! All variable

XPS 313 @ 700 eV Cu 3p, Cl 2s, O 1s, N 1s, VB x30 Z = 19

~~@ 720 eV~~

XPS 314 @ 720 eV B 1s x30 Z = 19

Z → 17

315 XPS @ 700 eV, Z = 17, Cu 3p, Cl 2s, O 1s, N 1s, VB x30 Z = 17

lost connection at scan 25, but seems fine

XAS 342 O-Kedge same spot (Z = 17)

XAS 343 Cu-Ledge same spot

XAS 344 O-Kedge new spot (Z = 19)

XAS 345 Cu-Ledge